

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

GA NUMBER: 730456

Design Circular: strategies and tools

Document Information

Report name	Design Circular: strategies and tools
Version number	2.2
Document number	D2.2
Due date for deliverable	31/05/2021
Actual submission date	30/09/2021
Lead beneficiary	TU Delft

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730456

Document Information

Work package	WP2
Document number	D2.2
Report name	Design strategies and tools
Version number	final
Lead authors (Org)	Jelle Joustra (TU Delft)
Contributing authors (Org)	Ruud Balkenende (TU Delft)
Due date for deliverable	May 2021
Actual submission date	Sept. 2021

Dissemination level

PU: Public	X
PP: Restricted to other programme participants	
RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium	
CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730456

Summary

Composite materials are used in an increasing range of applications because of their versatile material properties. The material composition can be tailored to achieve high mechanical performance and enable long product lifetime. Recycling on the other hand is complex due to the inherent homogeneous nature of the materials. These characteristics illustrate the challenging position of composite materials in a circular economy. In a circular economy, stakeholders along the product value chain interact to preserve product value and retain resources in the economic system, rather than wasting them when the product reaches its end of life. These stakeholders include the product designers, material suppliers, manufacturers, service providers, users and recycling companies and various others involved with the product lifecycle. The product itself must be designed to enable such interactions and intended lifetime extension or recovery practices.

This document reports on the research into circular product design strategies and tools performed in project Ecobulk. Ecobulk brought together over 30 project partners from automotive, furniture and construction industry to develop and demonstrate cases of circular composite products. These redesign cases provided insights on which *circular strategies* could be pursued and which *design aspects* could be applied to realise those. These strategies and design aspects are brought together in a comprehensive design framework for circular composite products¹.

This report contains the following elements. First, chapter 1 describes the current state of composite materials in the context of a circular economy, as well as the setting of this report within project Ecobulk. Then, chapters 2 and 3 explore circular strategies and design aspects in literature and by consulting experts. Chapter 4 combines these explorations with insights from Ecobulk demonstrator development and case studies by design students, culminating in a circular product design framework for products containing composites in a circular economy. Chapters 5-9 report on the design and analysis of the demonstrator cases, while chapter 10 presents the results from the design case studies by design students. The research results, design framework and case examples together constitute a solid base and provide inspiration to designers developing new, circular, composite products.

¹ Parts of this report have been published in the following journal article:

Joustra, J., Flipsen, B., & Balkenende, R. (2021). Circular Design of Composite Products: A Framework Based on Insights from Literature and Industry. *Sustainability*, 13(13), 7223. MDPI AG. Available from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su13137223>

Abbreviations

ABS	Acryle Butadiene Styrene; a thermoplastic
CE	Conformité Européenne; marked on products complying to EU requirements
CRF	Centro Recherche di Fiat
DIY	Do it yourself; consumer based maintenance or construction activities
ELV	End of Life Vehicles; directive by the European Committee on processing requirements for end of life vehicles
EN	European Standards
EoL	End of Life
EoU	End of Use
EU	European Union
FRP	Fibre reinforced plastics
GFRP	glass fibre reinforced plastics
GPS	global positioning system
ISO	International Standards Organisation
MSDS	Material Safety Data Sheet
PC	Polycarbonate; a thermoplastic
PE	Polyethylene; thermoplastic
PLA	Poly-lactic acid; a thermoplastic
PP	Polypropylene; a thermoplastic
QR	Quick response (code); visual coding which can be scanned by smartphone or other to retrieve information
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (directive)
TDS	Technical datasheet
UV	Ultraviolet (light)
WPC	Wood-plastic composite

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1. Introduction

The current rate of consumption places excessive pressure on our global ecosystems, depleting resources and generating waste. The circular economy offers a promising alternative to lower the environmental burden [1,2]. It aims to prevent waste by design and to preserve economic and environmental value [3]. Product integrity is a key concept in the circular economy [4] and maintaining product functionality has preference over materials recovery [4,5]. Product value can be preserved through long life, lifetime extension, and product recovery approaches, while material value can be preserved through recycling. Thus, the circular economy is a driver for achieving a sustainable use of resources.

In the case of composites, the circular economy scheme can largely be applied as far as product integrity is involved, however materials integrity has some distinct aspects [6]. Composite materials enable long product lifetime because of the resistance to corrosion and fatigue [7,8] and provide opportunities for lifetime extension through maintenance and repairs [9,10]. However, no clear solutions have yet been found to close the loop at a materials level. Composite recycling processes tend to break down the composite into its constituting materials, thus losing the specific composite material properties [7,11]. As recycling processes severely degrade materials, recycling is barely viable economically [11]. Consequently, the majority of composite material is landfilled or incinerated, losing the material and its potential for reuse [12]. Thus, while composite materials provide many advantages, we need to improve on their end-of-life treatment.

End-of-life treatment processes and their position in a Circular Economy are currently being developed from various perspectives. An increasing number of countries banned landfilling or stipulated gate fees to incentivise recycling activities [11,13]. Additional regulations to direct materials towards reprocessing activities, similar to the end of life vehicles (ELV) directive [14], are expected for large composite consuming sectors such as wind energy [13,15]. To answer to these increasingly strict regulations, recycling processes are developed [16–19] and industrialised [20,21]. Project consortia from academia and industry aim to create closed value chains for composite products [22,23] or explore repurposing opportunities for current end-of-life material flows [24]. The increasing attention to reuse and recycling illustrates the necessity as well as the challenges, which can be attributed to the variation and complexity of composite materials.

Composites can be classified according to either their matrix or reinforcement fractions [25]. For the matrices, ceramics, polymers and metals are commonly used, of which polymers are by far the largest group [7] and form the focus of this study. Within polymer matrices, thermosets (mainly epoxides and polyesters) and thermoplastics can be distinguished. The market share of thermoplastic composites, relative to thermoset-based, is increasing: from 33% in 2012 to nearly 50% in 2017 [7,26]. Reinforcements come in the form of particles and fibres, ranging from short and randomly ordered to continuous and unidirectional aligned [25,27]. Glass fibres dominate the market with 99% in volume versus 1% for carbon fibres [28]. The final material properties can be tuned by many factors, of which the most important are the selection of matrix and reinforcements, mixture ratio, and reinforcement structure (orientations & dimensions) [25].

Opportunities for reuse and recycling of composites will increase if they are addressed in the design stage [7,8,29]. End-of-life processing can be anticipated in the design stage by starting from the process needs, followed by analysis of the product structure [30,31]. This approach requires intricate knowledge of the product use, to be able to evaluate its residual quality and the intended recovery process. However, information about the product life and end-of-life is only available to a limited extent in the design stage, which limits such approaches [32]. Thus, designing composite products for recovery means the designer has to integrate additional, but uncertain, requirements into an already complex design process; designers often require additional support for this task [29,33]. However, despite the growing attention towards end-of-life processing, design for the recovery of composite products remains largely unexplored [29,34,35].

Figure 1 Information flows in the product development process. Normally considered a linear process, circular product design implies additional feedback to account for insights & requirements from recovery in all preceding stages.

1.1. Report outline

This deliverable reports on the development of design strategies and demonstrators for composite products in project Ecobulk. The report builds on reports D2.2 v1 and D2.4 for development of the circular product design strategies. For evaluation of the final demonstrators, the report directly connects to D8.3: General & individual business models, where the circular strategies are explicitly connected to business models and to report D4.1 on the (re-)manufacture of the innovative composite product. Together, these deliverable reports on design, materials and business models provide a sound basis for evaluating the circular design approaches taken in the Ecobulk demonstrators.

The demonstrators are evaluated using the circular product design framework for products containing composites. This framework connects circular strategies to product design aspects; Circular strategies concern the product lifecycle and directly relate to business models, and design aspects concern realization and the “how” of implementing circular design measures. Chapter 2-4 presents the framework and provides descriptions of circular strategies and design aspects.

Each demonstrator is evaluated with the manufacturer of the product in chapters 5-9. The manufacturers and designers were interviewed on the redesign of the product. The circular product design framework was used to elicit which circular strategies and design aspects were selected. And how these are implemented in the specific demonstrator to adapt the product to the intended recovery pathways and stakeholders involved.

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1.2. Aim & approach

To make the circular economy concept more actionable in design practice, Den Hollander proposed the Circular Product Design framework which connects circular strategies to design aspects [36]. Circular strategies describe measures to preserve product or material integrity, i.e. remanufacturing or recycling, and have a strong connection to business models [1]. Design aspects relate to product realisation and provide insights as to how recovery can be anticipated by design intent, such as choices with respect to materials and connections [3]. Combined in a framework, these strategies and design aspects provide designers with a starting point for new circular product development.

The circular strategies and design aspects were collected through an expanded systematic literature review and by consulting experts on design of composite products for a circular economy. The Circular Product Design framework [36] was used as the basis for the analysis. In July 2020, we reviewed literature with the objective to

identify circular strategies and design aspects for products containing composites in a circular economy. The data collection was set up as a systematic literature review, which was expanded through snowballing.

The focus group sessions were organised as workshops at the Ecobulk general assembly in Koblenz, Germany, June 2018. The preliminary results of these sessions are described in deliverable report D2.4.

The Circular Product Design Framework for Composites was used to evaluate the demonstrator cases. For each case, the designer was interviewed about the circular strategies and design aspects chosen for the product redesign. Every demonstrator chapter is broken down into;

- X.1 Demonstrator description
- X.2 Circular Design evaluation
- X. Circular product design framework

2. Circular strategies

In Table 1, we list the circular strategies with references to the literature and example quotes from the expert consultation. We then used these to formulate brief descriptions of each strategy.

Table 1 Circular economy strategies for products containing composite materials

Circular strategies [references]	Description from the literature	Quotes from expert consultation
Long life [3,4,40– 45,5,8,9,31,36–39]	Ensuring long product lifetime by promoting long use and reuse of the product as a whole, through manufacturing physically durable products, resisting ageing, fatigue and corrosion, able to sustain wear & tear without failure.	“[incorporating] additives [in the material] to make the panel more scratch resistant”
Lifetime extension [3,4,36,39–43,46– 49,5,50,51,7– 9,12,31,32,34]	Extending the time in use through maintenance, repair, technical upgrading or adapting, by users or service personnel. This can be promoted by facilitating handling of the product and subsequent rework tasks.	“Repairing strategies favouring parts replacement and upgrades” “Design for disassembly (screws, reversible snapfits)”
Product recovery [3,4,40– 43,47,48,52,5,7,9,31, 32,34,36,39]	Returning products or parts to working condition, thereby increasing the number of use cycles.	“[Keep product parts] fixed so they don't drop off during use but come off easily and quickly during reman/refurbish”
Structural reuse [8,9,31,32,34,53–55]	Retrieving structural elements, preserving the material composition, through repurposing, resizing or reshaping product parts for reuse in another context or construction.	“Remove panel elements for another furniture” “Structure made of linear components like truss structures so components could be re-used in other products”
Recycling [3,4,32,37,38,40– 43,46– 48,5,49,52,53,56– 58,7–9,12,16,29,31]	Recovery of materials through thermal, chemical, or mechanical processes, resulting in raw materials (“recyclate”), aiming to close the materials loop.	“use of compatible materials [compatible with process and other materials in the product to warrant a good recyclate grade]” “[facilitate composite material] recovery from bulky waste”

2.1.1. Long life

Long life slows the flow of resources through the economic system by extending the utilization period of a product [5]. Therefore, products have to be durable and reliable in use [3]. The goal is to keep the product close to its original state at relatively little cost, thus preserving resources as well as design and manufacturing efforts. Both the experts and the literature emphasize the good fatigue and corrosion resistance properties of composite materials, enabling long product life spans [8,38]. Building on these beneficial characteristics, composite materials are often employed in mechanically optimised structures exposed to cyclic loads, where long operational lifetime and reliability are important [44].

To ensure a long life, products need to be protected against degradation. Load conditions and ageing affect product lifetime. Cyclic loads cause structural fatigue which can lead to a reduction in strength [44]. The fatigue behaviour of composite materials differs from that of metals, and is more difficult to predict and inspect. Understanding strength reduction in relation to time, loads and environmental conditions, as well as that resulting from impact damage, continues to be an important research topic [44]. Ageing, caused by environmental exposure, can lead to deterioration of the materials [8,9,37]; experts suggested countering such deterioration by applying a protective coating. Thus, degradation mechanisms need to be considered in the design of long living composite parts.

A long lifespan combined with use in mechanically optimised parts introduces additional demands on reliability and safe operation. These factors can be addressed by design. Design strategies for safe life, fail-safe and damage tolerance ensure reliable performance, but come at the cost of lifespan (replacement at fixed time intervals), inefficient structural design (redundant load paths) or increased material use (by high safety margins), respectively [45]. Developments in design, engineering, and computation have reduced these safety margins, but especially older products may be over dimensioned and still be in sound physical condition when rendered obsolete [9]. Thus, these design approaches ensure safe operation of the product, but may conflict with prolonging lifetime or minimising material usage. The gains of incorporating these strategies need to be carefully weighed in the design.

The physical condition of a product is not necessarily the driver for ending operational life. There are factors of a more contextual nature such as legislation or technological obsolescence that can end product use. Keeping the product in operations after its intended design lifetime requires additional certification and maintenance [8,59]. Technological obsolescence may challenge spare parts provision. Together, these factors decrease the economic incentive for continued operation [34].

2.1.2. Lifetime extension

Lifetime extension concerns all interventions taken during the product lifetime to prolong its use phase, for example through maintenance, repair, upgrades and adaptations [42]. Maintenance and repair depend on the type of damage and its occurrence, as well as damage growth in the material. Literature and experts noted opportunities for both thermosets as well as thermoplastic composites to be repaired on-site [9,51]. Many repair techniques and bond patches are available; application depends on considerations like time constraints, aesthetic and aerodynamic quality, as well as residual strength and restoration [50].

The opportunities for lifetime extension depend on the product design as well as its operational context. Upgrades and adaptations can answer to changes in e.g. user desires and legislation, which means time becomes an explicit factor in design [41]. Therefore, the use of roadmaps is recommended [3]. Use scenarios that are predefined in the design stage may also serve to estimate degradation and residual quality, and thereby lifetime extension potential at end-of-use [32]. In practice, lifetime extension is considered feasible for composite products, depending on the product state [34].

2.1.3. Product recovery

Product recovery aims to increase the number of use cycles through refurbishment and remanufacturing of products [5,41]. It also includes harvesting of parts to reuse them as spares for lifetime extension measures [3]. Experts pointed out that these strategies are already applied to various composite products including car and

aircraft parts, for example [7,9], but also to larger structures like wind turbine blades. For the latter, refurbished blades offer short lead times and choice from a range of model at a reduced cost compared to new models [9]. As with long life and lifetime extension strategies, assessment of the structural state of the material is crucial, yet challenging for composite materials [50].

2.1.4. Structural reuse

Structural reuse was identified as a strategy to preserve material integrity. Structural reuse takes place through repurposing, resizing, or reshaping the product. These actions discard the original product function, but maintain the unique structural properties, determined by the combination of material composition and structural design [8]. Experts and the literature both note that the approach preserves material quality and value with a relatively small investment of energy and resources [8,9,53].

Applications of structural reuse were explored in occasional projects [8,9]. Large parts of wind turbine blades have been used to construct outdoor furniture and a playground. The building and construction industry could also reuse these recovered elements, but scalable applications have thus far been challenged by design and materials complexity [55]. It is expected that segmenting large parts into (standardised) construction elements like panels and beams will result in more diverse reuse opportunities [9].

2.1.5. Material recycling

Material recycling options for composites are determined by the matrix material, while most value is found in retrieved fibres [56]. Thermoplastic matrix composites can be remoulded into new products, while thermoset reprocessing is usually based on polymer degradation and aimed at fibre recovery [49,56]. The experts stressed the inherent complexity of the materials: there are few standardised composite formulations, and often additional materials are used like core materials, adhesives, and metal inserts. Generic recycling problems apply for collection, identification, separation, and sorting of the material and contamination in the reprocessing stage [58].

Figure 2 Adapted value hill for composite products in a circular economy

The value hill shows the position of circular strategies in the product lifecycle (Figure 2). On the left, materials are used to create parts, which are then assembled into products, to be distributed and installed. With each step of this process, the value embedded in the product increases. Then, the circular economy strategies come into play, aiming to preserve this embedded value for as long as possible, starting with the Long life strategy on the top. The strategies of Lifetime extension, product recovery serve to return functional products and parts to regular use. Structural reuse and materials recycling aim to close the materials loop. Similar but reversed to the production stage, the embedded value decreases. This visualises the benefits of aiming for high product or material integrity in recovery.

Table 2 shows the framework of design aims, circular economy strategies and associated actions or processes. The design aims distinguish between preserving product and material integrity [4], and the strategies show the effect on the product or material lifetime. The actions and processes show which activities are involved.

Adaptations to the initial Circular Product Design framework [36] are printed in bold. These changes pertain to the design aim of preserving material integrity. Structural reuse was added as additional strategy, positioned between product recovery and material recycling. In addition, the applicable processes for composite materials were added for both structural reuse and materials recycling.

Table 2 Circular design strategies for composite products, additions for composite materials in bold

Design aim	Preserving product integrity			Preserving material integrity	
circular economy Strategies	Long life	Lifetime extension	Product recovery	Structural reuse	Material recycling
Actions / Processes	Physical-durability Long use Reuse	Repair Maintenance Adapt Upgrade	Refurbishment Remanufacture Parts - harvesting	Repurpose Resize Reshape	Remould Mechanical Thermal Chemical

3. Design aspects

We identified 24 design aspects for products containing composite materials. To further structure the design aspects, we looked for patterns in the coded data. As evident in the co-occurrence analysis, the design aspects were strongly interconnected; all design aspects related to one or more of the others and the number of connections varied per aspect. Mapping out the co-occurrences provided an initial clustering of four clusters. We identified four themes: (cluster i) handling and rework, (cluster ii) product architecture, (cluster iii) product specifications and (cluster iv) product traceability. In tables 3 to 6, the design aspects are listed per cluster with references to and a description from the literature, and the associated design guidelines for each aspect.

To support implementation in design practice, the four initial clusters were related to the design process at large. shows the design aspects related to the stages of conceptual, embodiment and detail design, as described by Pahl et.al. [31]. This positioning makes the design aspects more accessible to design engineers by providing a starting point and a structure for applying them in the product development process.

Table 3 Design aspects for products containing composite materials in a circular economy, clustered and related to the stages in the product development process [31]

Concept design	Embodiment design		Detail design
cluster i: Handling & rework	cluster ii: Product architecture	cluster iii: Product specifications	cluster iv: Traceability
Accessibility	Connection selection	Material selection	Documentation
Adaptability	Dis- & reassembly	Structural design	Identification
Cleanability	Modularity	Manufacturing process	Monitoring
Ergonomics	Keying	Surface treatments	Standardisation
Fault isolation	Function Integration		
Functional packaging	Redundancy		
Interchangeability	Sacrificial elements		
Malfunction signalling			
Simplification			

3.1. Handling and rework

Table 4 Design aspects to facilitate handling and rework of products containing composites in a circular economy (cluster i)

Design aspects [References]	Description from the literature	Design guidelines
Accessibility [3,31,36,41,43,47,48,52]	Ensuring (internal) parts and materials as well as their connections can be reached and/or removed easily, keeping them at maximum utility level, and facilitating separation & sorting.	Platform design Using a disassembly map Grouping parts and/or materials in modules Access from one side, using a single tool Connections / fasteners that are easily identifiable and removable
Adaptability [4,36,40,41,55]	Anticipating and enabling changes and adjustments to be made to the product during its (successive) use cycle(s).	Multifunctional design Facilitate DIY solutions/adaptations Versatile, customisable layout of the components; adaptable/changing the (surface) colour Transformable system, and reversible assembly
Cleanability [31,41–43,47]	Making products, parts, and surfaces so that they can be cleaned or prevent accumulation of dirt.	Smooth surfaces Accessible and demountable parts & modules, especially where dirt accumulates Use of the same cleaning method, and materials & surfaces withstanding the same chemicals
Ergonomics [29,31,36]	Ensuring the product can be used, maintained, reworked, and reprocessed in a safe and efficient way.	Dis- and reassembly as needed, with accessible component & connections
Fault isolation [3,29,31,36,43,47]	Enabling tracking an occurring fault to its cause, e.g., a worn component, for quick and easy repair.	Develop and promote repair diagnostics Making (approaching) failure noticeable for users or service inspections
Functional packaging [31,36,40,41,47]	Choosing packaging for the product and/or components to optimise transport and distribution.	Reducing packaging weight and volume, Improving stackability and handling Ensuring product/component protection
Interchangeability [3,36,43,47,55]	Making parts or subassemblies of the product readily replaceable or exchangeable.	Interfaces that allow exchange of parts Matching dimensions and functions of parts and replacements Standard, accessible and dismountable parts, modules, and connections
Malfunction signalling [36,43,47]	Indicating (imminent) product failure to facilitate inspection and subsequent actions.	Accessible parts Indicating elements, e.g., wearing strips Monitoring of components
Simplification [31,36,41,47]	Minimising the complexity of the product in terms of functionality, assembly, appearance, and materials composition.	Select the simplest design option available Reduce the number of material types, components, and assembly steps

3.2. Product architecture

Table 5 Design aspects to construct the product architecture of products containing composites in a circular economy (cluster ii)

Design aspects [References]	Description from the literature	Design guidelines
Connection selection [3,7,8,37,40,41,43,47,52,55]	Selecting connections that can be accessed, opened, and reused where appropriate to facilitate use, rework, and recovery actions during product life.	Reversibility; e.g., screws, clips and several types of snapfits Recovery action, operator (e.g., user or service personnel), tool types (that need to be) available, Material compatibility and use resistance (e.g., wear and ageing)
Dis- and reassembly [3,5,52,7,29,31,36,40,41,47,48]	Facilitating manual or mechanical disassembly and reassembly of the product to enable reuse of parts to improve the recovery rate.	Using reversible connections (e.g., screws), and avoiding in-moulded inserts Mechanical assembly systems (e.g., form fits) Optimised and short component disassembly paths Use commonly available, standard, accessible tools, and connections.
Function integration [40]	Combining multiple functions and (sub)components into one part.	Integration of connectors with parts Combine structural design and other functions, e.g. aesthetic or aerodynamic
Keying [36,47]	Using product shape to facilitate alignment, e.g., holes and pins	Using pins, grooves, and other mating shapes for alignment and placing components
Modularity [3,4,52,55,7,8,29,36,40,41,43,47]	Grouping features within the product to create sub-assemblies that are accessible, removable, and interchangeable.	Match lifetime or maintenance intervals of components, Sort chemically similar materials, or isolate hazardous substances, Allow for (functional) customisation and adaptation
Redundancy [31,36,41]	Adding additional materials or functionality to ensure continued operation and safety, even when parts degrade or are (partially) removed.	Add materials on wearing areas Integrate multiple, redundant, load paths Add excess functionality
Sacrificial elements [36,40]	Defining replaceable components and surface treatments to take up wear and damage, thus protecting other parts.	Identify the areas subject to degradation Apply protective surface treatments Apply protective elements, e.g., covers

3.3. Product specifications

Table 6 Design aspects concerning product specifications of products containing composites in a circular economy (cluster iii)

Design aspects [References]	Description from the literature	Design guidelines
Material selection [5,7,47– 49,52,59,8,16,29,36, 37,40,41,43]	Selecting matrix, reinforcement, connections, and other materials to perform optimally for the use phase, as well as recovery stage of the product. For composites, this includes the type and orientation of reinforcements.	Consider reprocessing compatibility, by e.g., using chemically similar matrix & reinforcement (self-reinforced composites), avoiding mix of biological and technological materials Using recycled and recyclable materials, thermoplastic or reversible thermoset matrices and short fibres, and limit the number of materials used within an assembly to promote recyclability Reconsider hazardous chemicals, effect of ageing (e.g., discolouring & loss of quality) Selection to cope with hostile conditions, to prolong lifetime
Manufacturing process selection [7,8,37,40,43,59]	Selecting and optimising the process to minimise emissions and meet the material, functional, shape and recovery criteria.	Optimise fibre architecture. Automate manufacturing for consistency Reduce waste & emissions of manufacturing process; consumables (foils, tapes, etc.) and material offcuts, especially when impregnated with resin Allow recycled content uptake
Structural design [7,8,29,31,41]	Optimising the material structure, shape, and product architecture to achieve the desired structural performance.	Use form stiffness and load bearing shapes Integrate form and material placement to meet load cases Consider reusable structural elements
Surface treatments [3,7– 9,16,31,36,37,41,52]	Selecting coatings and other surface treatments appropriate for the use, reuse and reprocessing of the product and its materials.	Protective gelcoats, paints, tapes, foils, or other treatments to prevent material degradation by UV radiation, moisture, or erosion Use non-hazardous substances to support rework and reprocessing Ensure materials including surface treatments compatibility in the recycling process

3.4. Traceability

Table 7 Design aspects to facilitate traceability of products containing composites in a circular economy (cluster iv)

Design aspects [References]	Description from the literature	Design guidelines
Documentation [7– 9,29,31,40,43,48,54,55]	Providing information about the product, components, and functions to stakeholders in the value chain and actors in the product and component lifecycle.	Identify which information the actors need, and how, e.g.: Design specifications; e.g., dimensions, assembly, part id’s, material composition Service manuals and repair tutorials Certification and standards Material passports
Identification [7–9,29,31,36,43,47]	Using labels, tags etc. to facilitate recognition of the product, parts, materials and/or its specifications.	Labelling products & components Defining material characteristics for separation processes (i.e., IR scanning, density) Placing material markings on parts Mixing in markers into the materials
Monitoring [8,41,43]	Determining and logging of product properties and use conditions over the product lifetime.	Regular inspection intervals Embedded monitoring devices Sample or coupon testing (e.g., fatigue, strength) of used components Internet of Things solutions Digital measurement and identification systems
Standardisation [3,5,47,48,54,55,8,9,29, 31,36,40,41,43]	Using well known, defined, and widely used components, processes, dimensions, materials etc. in the product design, or developing a standard layout for the product(range). This design aspect relates, but is not restricted to, industry standardisation.	Standardisation comes in many forms, e.g.: Components (connections, bearings, etc) Construction codes Dimensional tolerances Certification and inspection procedures Standard layout across product (range) Basic or standard available tools

Concept design is about exploring solutions in the first stages of the product development process. The related design aspects are further elaborated in cluster i, and mostly aim to facilitate handling and rework actions, such as “Design for Accessibility”. Adaptability was mostly recognised by the experts as a way to make a product “suitable for different uses” by making multifunctional or evolving structures. Most rework includes some form of cleaning, gaining access (opening) to the product, and inspecting imminent malfunctions or already occurred faults, followed by interchanging parts. The users and service personnel involved benefit from a simple and ergonomic product design where ease of disassembly and reassembly are important. These conceptual design solutions set the stage for further embodiment of the product.

Embodiment design entails engineering these initial solutions into the product architecture in cluster ii. Here, the designer constructs the product layout, how the product and its subassemblies are built and interconnected. The literature and experts often referred to modular approaches and careful selection of connections and keying features. Integrating functions and multiple components into a single optimised part is one of the main potential benefits of using composite materials. Experts recognised this as an opportunity to accumulate functions, and thereby mass into a single component, increasing its potential value for recycling. The level of integration has to be carefully considered based on the prospective product use cycles. Redundancy relates to the design strategies of “Safe life”, “Fail safe” and “Damage tolerant”. These design aspects construct a product architecture of which the part properties need to be further specified.

Embodiment design also includes defining the product specifications in cluster iii. This requires selection of the manufacturing process, surface treatments and materials, as well as structural design. Some products may require built-in redundancy or (additional) sacrificial elements. The experts mostly regarded material selection as a means to make the product more recyclable. For example, experts suggested “Creating materials with inherent aesthetic properties”, to avoid coatings and thereby material contamination in the recycling process. With the specifications known, the design is ready to proceed to the final stage: detailing.

The **detail design** stage includes design aspects that facilitate tracing back product information in cluster iv. To facilitate recovery, the product has to be identifiable, and its initial specifications should be laid down in appropriate documentation. Documentation of the product specifications and instructions –and making these available to the designated stakeholders- serves to solve the information gap that hampers many actual recovery processes. For example, experts also suggested “attaching information to the product” to inform the user on return options, stimulating and supporting collection at end of use. Literature and experts both proposed standardisation of components, materials, and assembly systems to facilitate processing. Standardisation of tests and certification procedures, as well as monitoring actions also support assessing the current product state. Monitoring can serve to extend knowledge on the original product characteristics to the state at end-of-use. These design aspects support the availability of product information, which is key for efficient recovery actions and effective value retrieval.

3.5. Additional design considerations

The demonstrator case evaluation delivered several additional aspects to take into consideration when developing circular composite products. *Circular narrative* and *Collaboration* concern involving users, suppliers, resellers and other stakeholders in realizing a closed loop for the product. *Material variability* relates to the intricacies of sourcing and processing recovered materials which directly relates to *Traceability and control* and *Timing* the return flows. *Physical durability*, increasing product robustness to withstand degradation and as such enable product longevity, brings specific requirements to the product design and material formulations. These aspects are further elaborated in the table below and in the respective demonstrator cases.

Table 8 Additional design considerations observed in the Ecobulk case analysis

<i>Circular design factors</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>Incentives</i>	Conenor	Products need to be recollected and returned to the manufacturer or other (licensed) reprocessing companies for recycling. These channels do not exist yet for many materials, and there are no economic, regulatory or other commercial drivers. To realise a fully closed resource loop, incentives could be put in place to motivate return of materials.
<i>Circular narrative, circular storytelling</i>	Moretti, Microcab, Design students	Conveying the circular concept of the product to stakeholders in the product value chain including partner companies as well as users. Through documentation or the design itself.
<i>Material variability</i>	All	Recycled materials differ from virgin materials in the sense that these typically have a larger deviation of properties. This means additional measures are needed to reach the desired mechanical properties (CRF), process the agglomerate (Conenor), but also brings interesting design challenges, in creating products with visual and aesthetic clues to the material's origin (Moretti, Microcab).
<i>Traceability & control</i>	Moretti	Degraded panels can be recycled through existing centralised channels. A tracking and control mechanism was suggested to optimise the logistics of returning and replacing parts & materials.
<i>Collaboration</i>	Conenor, Moretti	To ensure recollection of the materials, it was suggested to exploit the currently existing product value chains. However, the additional tasks may deviate from current stakeholder activities and business models. Collaboration and sharing incentives along the value chain are necessary to close the loop.
<i>Physical durability</i>	All	Physical durability is taken into account when the product is subject to degradation in-use (e.g wear and tear) or from environmental conditions, most notably UV exposure. The physical durability can be tuned to prolong the lifespan of the product for as long as possible (Conenor, Moretti) or align it to the expected service intervals (Microcab) or system lifespan (CRF, MAIER).
<i>Timing, planning and roadmaps</i>	Automotive	Timing of recovery loops is needed to keep the current product functioning, but also as sourcing mechanism for future material needs.

4. Circular product design framework

The Circular Product Design framework brings these perspectives together and shows, as can be expected, considerable overlap in the findings from the literature and expert consultations, although we found more conceptual solutions in the literature. This may indicate that the focus of experts primarily lies on the technological aspects of embodiment and detail design, whereas the literature tends to explore new directions.

Concerning the strategies, most design aspects were identified for lifetime extension and product recovery. Fewer design aspects were found for material recycling, while structural reuse was only encountered incidentally. Structural reuse as a recovery pathway has been a topic of discussion in the field of composite materials, but is generally not addressed in circular product design literature.

Seven design aspects were added to address the specific characteristics of composite materials. Composites clearly distinguish themselves from other bulk processing materials in the way they integrate internal and external product properties. Internal properties such as material selection are defined by the designer, to create external properties that the user observes, such as product function and performance [60,61]. Composite material properties can be tailored, even locally, to achieve the desired external properties, which provides opportunities for function integration within a single component. Moreover, the material, and thereby its exact properties, is created at the same time as the product itself, and as such is highly subject to manufacturing process conditions. Thus, the material formulation is an integral part of the design and production process. Therefore, function integration, structural design, and manufacturing process selection were added to the framework.

Determining the residual quality of composite materials can be challenging as defects are not always observable from the product's surface. To support quality assessments and reprocessing, documentation and monitoring were added to the Circular Product Design framework. Documentation, such as product or material passports, is often seen as enabler for many recovery pathways and servicing activities [62]. A greater understanding of material behaviour over time, in relation to factors like load history, environmental exposure and impact damage remains a topic of ongoing research [63,64].

4.1.1. Connections within the framework

The Circular Product Design framework shows that many design aspects are related to multiple strategies, and that the circular strategies have many design aspects in common. For implementation this has several consequences which have also been observed in other design frameworks [36,43,45]. The circular strategies of lifetime extension and product recovery largely connect to the same aspects, indicating that these strategies are, to a large extent, similar from a design perspective. Long life and recycling, however, pose very different demands, which is reflected in the more distinct set of design aspects they connect to.

The design aspects themselves cannot be regarded as stand-alone factors in product design. Addressing a particular design aspect is likely to affect multiple strategies. This might lead to tensions regarding the appropriate design intervention, as a specific embodiment of a design aspect might be simultaneously positive for one strategy but negative for another. For example, surface treatments may enable a long product life, but they may contaminate a recycling process. The Circular Product Design framework (Table 9) provides an overview of potential tensions, and thus raises awareness concerning the effect of design decisions on their realisation of circular strategies that can be taken into account during the early stages of product development. In addition to the tensions between strategies, there are various connections and interdependencies between design aspects.

The design aspects were strongly interconnected. There are different reasons for these connections, which have also been encountered in earlier studies [36,43]. First, some design aspects are obvious and therefore often-mentioned when discussing product design or recovery aims. For example, material selection is often connected to identification and standardisation to improve recycle quality. Second, both the literature and experts build on each-others' insights, resulting in a subset of design aspects often noted in conjunction. Third, there are many well-known relations and interdependencies between design aspects which makes it logical to discuss them together. For example, modularity is often discussed in relation to dis- and reassembly [7,29,31]. These connections need to be addressed in the product design process. Thus, the designer has to account for connections and interdependencies between design aspects which have been made explicit in the Circular Product Design framework.

The connections between design aspects could result in implicit implementation of multiple design aspects during the product development process. As one novice designer pointed out "although it was a design process, I did not need to design every step, some followed logically from what I already did" [Rödtrad] and another reported "to be surprised how many design aspects had actually been

implemented in the final concept” [Gúlia]. Despite these relations, both novice and expert designers recognised that the nature of the connections and manifestation of design aspects in the product design is case dependent and that the effect needs to be assessed for different design aspects separately. The relations can strengthen each other, but also adversely affect the intended recovery actions. i.e. the fastener selection determines to a large extent if and how a product can be disassembled. The suggestion of presenting the design aspects in “package solutions” based the identified relations was therefore discarded.

Table 9 Circular Product Design framework for composites in a circular economy, connections between circular strategies and design aspects indicated with coloured dots. Grey; CPD framework, Green; Ecobulk demonstrators, Yellow; novice designer cases

Design aim	Product integrity			Materials integrity	
	Long life	Lifetime extension	Product recovery	Structural reuse	Material recycling
Concept design					
Accessibility		● ●	●		● ●
Adaptability	●	● ● ●	● ●	●	
Cleanability	●	● ●	●		●
Dis-&reassembly	●	● ● ●	● ● ●	●	● ●
Ergonomics	●	● ●	●		
Fault isolation	●	● ●	●		●
Functional packaging		●	●		●
Interchangeability		● ● ●	● ●	●	●
Malfunction signalling	●	●	●		
Simplification	● ●	● ●	● ●		●
Embodiment					
Connection selection	● ●	● ● ●	● ●	●	● ●
Function integration	●	● ●	●		● ●
Keying		● ● ●	●		
Material selection	● ●	● ● ●	●	●	● ● ●
Manufacturing		● ●	● ●		● ●
Modularity		● ● ●	● ● ●	●	● ●
Redundancy	●	●	●		
Sacrificial elements	●	● ● ●	●		●
Structural design	● ● ●	● ● ●	● ●	●	● ●
Surface treatments	● ●	● ● ●	● ●		● ● ●
Detail design					
Documentation		● ● ●	● ●	●	● ●
Identification		● ●	● ●	●	● ●
Monitoring	● ●	● ● ●	● ●		
Standardisation		● ● ●	● ● ●	●	● ●
Circular storytelling			●		●
Timing & planning		●	●		●

4.2. Implementation in Ecobulk & student design cases

In project Ecobulk, the partners developed both design strategies and functional demonstrator products. A baseline of design strategies was described in the initial report D2.2 “Design strategies and tools, version 1”, and further explored during workshop sessions at the general assembly in Koblenz. These explorations led to the development of an initial design framework, which was used as guidance during demonstrator development and student design cases. In turn, the demonstrators in the three product sectors were used to further develop, refine and expand upon the design framework.

4.2.1. Circular strategy selection

At the level of product integrity, the demonstrator cases most often selected long life and product recovery as primary strategies. The product lifetime and thereby implementation of the Long life strategy was driven by the initial use case. Long product lifetime showed a clear advantage in the construction and furniture cases. This was different for the automotive sector. Two of the automotive cases had limited opportunities for prolonging lifetime of the demonstrator product. MAIER and CRF worked on interior components which are part of the complete vehicle assembly. Addressing vehicle lifetime as a whole was out of scope of this project, and thus formed a boundary condition for individual component lifetime. Microcab on the other hand has the opportunity to design the complete vehicle lifecycle and developed a lifecycle planning. The planning scheduled maintenance, refurbishment and recycling of specific groups of components. In the end, the demonstrator cases chose to pursue product recovery strategies. Incidental implementation of long life strategies followed from the use case rather than circular objectives.

At the materials level, structural reuse was not implemented, but all cases took recycling of the case product into material agglomerates into account. For the construction sector the recycling approach was chosen as demonstrator development was driven by Conenor’s agglomeration and extrusion technology, which is based on a recycling strategy using shredded composite fragments as filler. The furniture case aims to reduce toxic emissions and recyclability of particleboard through new particle board materials and binder formulations, developed with KEAS and AKZO. In the automotive sector, recycling targets are defined by the ELV directive, which must be achieved and proven for all new models. The automotive demonstrators, all dashboard components, are seen as subject to the vehicle as a whole, including lifespan and End of Life treatments. CRF and MAIER, both established industry players in this context, therefore focused on bulk recycling into plastic compounds. Microcab however, chose to disconnect vehicle life from component life by introducing refurbishment intervals. The refurbishment intervals prolong vehicle lifespan, and ensure effective recollection of end-of-use parts for recycling. This approach may however lead to an increase of refurbishment and recycling activity, since the scheduled intervals are shorter (7 years) than an average vehicle lifespan in Europe (12 years) [65]. Still, the volume of materials to recycle is offset by the fact that only a part of the car (interior) is retrieved, rather than the complete car. Thus, despite different approaches and rationale, recycling was universally regarded as required strategy to be incorporated in the development of a circular product.

4.2.2. Design aspects: Expanding the framework

Several additional identified design factors can be added to the framework. *Circular storytelling* is added to the framework as design aspect, as it presents a means to the designer to evoke desirable user (inter)actions. In earlier studies by Sumter et. al., *Circular Economy storytelling* was identified to be important for communications and collaboration in a circular economy design project [66]. However, Sumter also noted that the newness of the field and lack of a formal vocabulary causes confusion. While such confusion was not encountered in the communication towards end-users, agreeing on terminology and goals was an important factor in communication within Ecobulk. MAIER, for example, recalled that the framing of circular economy was new to them, but to a large extent found to align with familiar eco-design practices.

Also *Timing & planning* are added, as these activities become essential for closing the loop and ensuring timed and organized return resource flows [3].

A number of additional aspects has been observed, but was not included in the framework. These aspects are not directly part of the product design process as such, but should be aligned to it to develop a circular product. *Traceability & control*, and *collaboration* are often highlighted as essential elements for developing a functioning supply chain, where *Incentives* are shared, rather than individually optimized [67]. *Material variability* is a near-inevitable consequence of working with reclaimed resources, and is as such one of the major challenges for developing a circular product. These are therefore not added to the design strategy framework, but should anyhow be considered in circular product development.

The implementation of the design framework was case specific. Circular strategies and design aspects were selected for each case individually. Through evaluation of the cases we observed some notable differences as well as similarities across the cases.

4.2.3. Embodiment and implementation

The embodiment of design aspects was case specific. This followed from the differences in context and design approaches across the demonstrator cases. Connection selection for example, is highly standardised in the automotive sector. Such standards originate from certification requirements as well as assembly lines, leading to a restricted set of available options. Furniture and construction demonstrators were less restricted by such requirements and adapted the fastener selection at a later stage in the project. Overall, the different approaches to similar design aspects illustrate the use of the design framework in practice.

The novice designers were not bound to a specific manufacturing or market context. This gave them space to develop the case and concept in the early stages of the project. Both case and concept were refined in the course of the project, using design probes – rapid prototypes – to explore boundary conditions and solution principles. Much like the co-evolution of the problem-solution space as described by Dorst, where prototype development serves to test the proposed solution, as well as deepen understanding of the design problem at hand [68]. Not restricting themselves to industry practices led the students to develop new fasteners and reconfigurable panel systems. This in contrast to the Ecobulk cases, where such systems are standardised and dictated by assembly line requirements.

Initially, the framework was used as a checklist to identify relevant design aspects for the case at hand. In this stage, the framework supported stating requirements and formulating a design brief. Further detailed descriptions or design guidelines for the design aspects were deemed unnecessary, as the current list of design aspects tied in well with existing knowledge and experience. This allowed the framework to be applied to the variety of cases, and allowed the designers to implement the design aspects fitting to the case at hand. Thus, the current level of detail was deemed adequate for the developed demonstrator cases, and supported the designers in creating an overview and formulating a design brief.

The novice designers took a more explorative approach in the project. The initial assignment was refined by investigating business models, material properties and target groups. In addition to detailing the case definition, the designers gained valuable insights that enriched their creativity in problem solving. These ideas were often evaluated through rapid prototyping and testing, allowing for quick iterations on the design. Thus, the design case by novice designers presents a strong learning component, that stimulated their creativity in developing design solutions.

The circular product design framework connected well to design practice. Designers in Ecobulk used the framework as a checklist, and detailed the design further based on their pre-existing knowledge on design solutions for their specific context. The novice designers used the framework to get an initial overview of the case, which was then further developed in an explorative and iterative way. Implementation of the design aspects went smoothly, as these connected directly to their design approach and envisioned solutions. Thus, the design framework supports designers bringing in their individual and context specific skills into the circular design case at hand.

4.3. Limitations and Recommendations

The aim of this study was to provide an overview of circular strategies and design aspects for composite products in a Circular Economy. The results of this study are quite generic due to the width of the initial scope. However, the constructed framework has demonstrated its use in practice. A preliminary version of the framework [6] has successfully been used in product development [22], analysis of design case studies [69] and for standard development through a CEN Workshop Agreement [70]. Thus, the Circular Product Design framework for composite products is a first step in designing products containing composite materials for a circular economy. However, the framework could be further refined and expanded. The strategy of structural reuse should be further investigated, exploring its potential across different industry sectors and product types. The set of design aspects should be further expanded by investigating additional case studies. Building on this, the collected design aspects and design guidelines could then form the foundation of a design catalogue. Implementation of the framework in the product development process has to be further detailed. Further research, building on design studies with composite products, will be carried out to validate and build the framework.

The presented strategies focus on prolonging product lifetime and preserving resources, but do not explicitly account for safety issues involved with composite materials. Risks are found across the composite product life and include release of volatile organic compounds, fibres & particles and dust [71,72]. All of these pose a threat to human health and the environment. Zappeloni [72] discusses best practices to minimise such emissions in the manufacturing stage, and Medici expressed concerns over long term outdoor exposure [73]. Also (re)processing, which aims to separate, or at least downsize the materials, risks hazardous emissions [7,71,74]. Thus, next to preserving resources, additional measures are needed to address human, environmental and ecological impacts of manufacturing, using and reprocessing composite materials.

Contamination of the materials in the recycling stage remains a challenge. Undesired mixing hampers reprocessing as most processes benefit from or even rely on a well-defined material input in order to deliver a good quality recyclate. For reuse, mixing of different material types should be avoided, to prevent further complicating the materials composition for future recovery. Solutions to prevent or cope with material contamination are developed in materials [7,75,76] and reprocessing technology [11] and should be addressed in the product design [7,29]. All of these relate to the development of a market for recycled composite materials. Appropriate and scalable reuse applications are needed to assign value to the recyclate and as such provide an economic rationale for recovery [58,75].

4.4. Conclusions

This report collects insights from project Ecobulk in a design framework and presents the resulting demonstrator cases. Together, the framework and demonstrators serve as guidance and inspiration for the design of new, circular composite products.

Composite materials offer great opportunities for product development and high performance in use, but their position in a circular economy system is challenging. The increased use and increasing volume of end-of-life material have led to increased attention from governments, industry and academia.

Project Ecobulk set out to demonstrate how products containing composite materials can be designed to close resource loops in a circular economy, based on insights from literature, industry partners and novice designers. These insights are brought together in an adapted Circular Product Design framework for Composites. The circular economy strategies are largely similar to reported strategies as far as product integrity is involved. However, recovery pathways focusing on material integrity show distinct opportunities for composite reuse, in particular, structural reuse. The strategy, positioned between product recovery and material recycling, has the potential to preserve composite material value at a

relatively low cost. Moreover, the characteristics of composite materials cannot be regarded without reference to their structural shape. Structural reuse retains the material composition and structure, yet relieves it from its initial function, making the material available for reuse and repurposing in other applications.

We identified 26 design aspects for products containing composites, the majority of which aligned with earlier Circular Product Design frameworks derived for different design areas. Because composite materials differ from conventional bulk materials in the way they are processed and created, seven additional design aspects were added to the framework. Most notable of these are structural design and function integration. Both these design aspects build on the potential of composite materials to integrate form and functionality to achieve optimal performance, in the first use phase as well as in subsequent ones.

The identified strategies and design aspects are highly interconnected, which signals that designers need a clear overview of the product design as well as its planned use cycles, and the stakeholders involved. Circularity adds requirements to an already complex task of composite product design and material engineering. The Circular Product Design framework for composites aims to support designers and researchers to create an overview and to integrate circular design measures into products containing composite materials. Further studies could expand on and detail the framework by analysing cases and through implementation in new product development. As such, the framework is considered a first step towards providing insights into available circular strategies and design aspects and their interrelations, to support designers developing new composite products for a circular economy.

From the interviews it became apparent that designers collect their knowledge from a range of sources. This includes education, working experience, discussions and reading up on specific topics. An important role was reserved for “learning by doing”, developing new insights through product development and learning from case examples.

5. Construction: Conenor

5.1. Demonstrator description

The construction sector demonstrators evolved around the materials developed and supplied by Conenor. Four demonstrator sites were developed in Finland, France and Portugal focusing on outdoor use of the construction materials. These demonstrator activities are introduced in report D2.4 and further elaborated in D2.6. This design evaluation focuses on the water fountain shelter in Lipor Park, Portugal. This demonstrator case represents the challenges and opportunities of using these specific materials in a climate of with high temperatures and exposure to UV radiation.

This chapter starts by listing the circular strategies and design aspects for the construction demonstrator. These observations are annotated to pictures of the Lipor park shelter, to put them into context, and brought together in a framework table to show interrelations between strategies and design aspects.

5.2. Circular design evaluation

5.2.1. Circular strategies

Conenor focused on facilitating recycling of the materials through development of new material formulations and production of recycled composite products. The materials are produced using the company's proprietary agglomeration and extrusion technology. The technology allows multiple loop recycling of the components containing reinforced plastic. Still, there are inevitable relations to other circular strategies.

These mostly concern strategies that benefit and prolong the first use case. For example, the material formulation is expected to last several years in outdoor use conditions, withstanding environmental degradation and erosion. Also, the toughened surfaces of the multilayer products facilitate cleaning, which supports lifetime extension by maintenance and making graffiti removable. Parts harvesting could be done incidentally but is not part of the initial strategy. The following table lists the major circular strategy considerations for the construction demonstrator.

Table 10 Circular strategies selected for the construction demonstrator case

<i>Circular strategy</i>	<i>Design considerations</i>
<i>Long life</i>	The material is formulated to last several years in outdoor use; the surface layers of the multimaterial extrusion profiles are toughened to prevent degradation of polymer chains. The design and materials used allow for longer life when compared to alternatives such as traditional wood-plastic composite, chemically treated wood and plywood and therefore support the benefits of a longer life product.
<i>Lifetime extension</i>	Broken parts can be replaced where necessary; bolted connections and screws are used to facilitate disassembly.
<i>Material recycling</i>	The material is fully recyclable in Conenor's proprietary process, a full production-use-reprocessing loop has been demonstrated in the project. The material formulation, design and assembly of the demonstrator enable disassembly, separation and reprocessing of the construction material. It is further expected the material is easy recyclable also in conventional extrusion processes commonly used in the market beyond the Conenor process.

5.2.2. Design aspects

Table 11 Design aspects implemented in the construction demonstrator case

<i>Design aspect</i>	<i>Implementation</i>
<i>Adaptability</i>	The components can be assembled into different structures to change functionality
<i>Cleanability</i>	The extruded materials have smooth, plastic rich surfaces with mineral additive to realise a hard & smooth (cleanable) surface. The PE-based profiles also use peroxide crosslinking to prevent polymer chain degradation. The non-porous surface does not get penetrated by water or dirt or graffiti and thus can be cleaned using high pressure washer (water).
<i>Dis- and reassembly</i>	Assembled using stainless steel screws and bolted joints. At the UK universities, the demonstrators are temporarily placed structures that must be disassembled later.
<i>Interchangeability</i>	Planks are replaceable if damaged by virtue of selected fasteners (removable) and standard range of construction material dimensions.
<i>Connection selection</i>	Stainless steel braces & bolts are used to stiffen the structure. Bolts & screws selected to allow for disassembly. Metal screws provided the best connection, but must be completely removed before reprocessing (ie. Sorting or magnetic separation).
<i>Material selection</i>	The use of recycled long fibre reinforced polymers materials brings advantages in terms of flexural strength, stiffness and water resistance and so lasts longer compared to e.g. plywood and wood plastic composites. Also opens up opportunities for more diverse use of secondary raw materials in outdoor construction products. PE crosslinking used to toughen material & prevent degradation of polymer chains. Use of thermoset GFRP-waste streams that have limited disposal routes and few commercial opportunities for reuse. The outer product surfaces of the products contain UV-stabilization additives as well as chemical compatibilizer for long life use. Materials can be reprocessed through agglomeration at Conenor or licenced party
<i>Manufacturing</i>	Manufacturing process accepts recycled agglomerate Process accepts thermoset FRP waste combined with thermoplastics Multilayer extrusion allows for specific surface treatments & formulations
<i>Structural design</i>	Stainless steel braces & bolts are used to stiffen the structure
<i>Surface treatment</i>	The multilayer extrusion process provides opportunities for surface treatments: uv, colouring, toughening or even fire retarding. No coatings needed as plastics can be coloured in the process, which minimises the number of materials in the recycling process.
<i>Documentation</i>	Material specification delivered with product Entry in end-user platform database Reuse suggestions & documentation provided to user & contractor Conenor keeps records of processed batches. These cannot be traced back to individual parts, but for Ecobulk demo's the small differences across the parts at a specific site do not hamper reprocessing
<i>Identification</i>	The Quick Response (QR) code attached to the product (WP5) leads to easy access to information guiding customers on options for dis/reassembly, spare parts and repurposing or materials recovery.
<i>Standardisation</i>	Standardised dimensions of construction materials International standards (EN, ISO) for this specific material (class) are needed to certify them in future when available, and thereby make them acceptable for large scale use
<i>Monitoring</i>	Regular inspections are advised to warrant safe use

Standardisation

In the construction demonstrator it was stressed that appropriate standardisation is required to create a scalable and attractive business case for the newly formulated construction material. Without such standards, the materials cannot be certified for application and will thus remain only usable at a demonstrator level.

5.2.3. Product specific strategies & design aspects

Incentives

Returning the product to the manufacturer: As no economic, regulatory or other commercial driver requires this, these channels do not exist yet. However, other similar composite product manufacturers like wood-plastic composite (WPC) existing in every country could easily recycle and utilize the material.

Linking back to the manufacturer would enable additional panels to be purchased if the product were to be reformulated into another product.

Conenor

Figure 3 Demonstrator annotated with Design aspects, colour coded by circular strategy.

5.3. Circular product design framework

5.3.1. Framework connections

The Circular product design framework for composites connects circular strategies to technological design aspects. The connections indicate how a specific strategy is realised in the design of the product, its constituent parts and composition of the materials. For example, Conenor uses the design aspect of Adaptability to enable product recovery (parts harvesting). As such, the framework provides an overview of which strategies and aspects are selected, but also how these connect.

Some design aspects connect to multiple strategies and vice versa. This can create tensions as well as opportunities in the design. Cleanability has obvious benefits for prolonging lifetime of a product. But Conenor took care to select materials, connections and surface treatments that enable a long life, through their resistance to environmental degradation & use case, as well as compatibility with the recycling process.

The framework below depicts the connections found for the construction demonstrator. Even though Conenor initially focused on material recycling, connections to other circular strategies are evident.

Table 12 Circular product design strategy framework, connections between circular strategies and design aspects for this demonstrator highlighted in green

Design aspects	Product Integrity			Materials Integrity	
	Long life	Lifetime extension	Product recovery	Structural reuse	Material recycling
Adaptability					
Cleanability					
Dis-&reassembly					
Interchangeability					
Connection selection					
Material selection					
Manufacturing					
Structural design					
Surface treatments					
Documentation					
Identification					
Monitoring					
Standardisation					

5.3.2. Implementation in design process

The Ecobulk construction demonstrator, mostly used the framework to structure the product development process. The framework was used with iterative dialogue between the four demonstrators and Conenor to define the optimal structures and components available to form an understanding of the circular system in which the product operates, and the strategies that are involved. This helped to get an overview of the product lifecycle and which product characteristics needed further attention in product development. As such, the framework helped to structure the thinking and thereby the design process.

The framework was also used as a communication tool. The circular strategies listed in the framework relate to business models and stakeholder actions. The align with the value chain map which was explored in D2.4 and the new product value chain that was further developed in WP8. Together, the design

framework and the developed product value chain were used to enter discussions with stakeholders along the product value chain.

The circular product design framework was deemed applicable to the design process. In the demonstrator development it could however not be used to its full extent. At the start of the project, a number of boundary conditions and the design tasks were already defined, limiting the use for analysing the case and developing new concepts. However, the structure it provided was found to be very valuable in entering discussions with stakeholders. Thus, in addition to supporting the design task itself, the design framework provides a valuable communication tool.

6. Furniture: Moretti Compact & Cosmob

6.1. Demonstrator description

The furniture demonstrator evolved around reconfigurable parts. The furniture pieces are built using a set of basic elements: 2 different size cubes and 'L' shaped cube elements. These can be reconfigured to make items for a bedroom and study area – desk, chair, bed, shelving units and a bedside table. The demonstrator products themselves are described in detail in D2.6.

This chapter presents the circular strategies and design aspects implemented in the furniture demonstrator. These are listed and then annotated to the demo picture, relating the observations to the design case. The circular strategies and design aspects are then connected in the framework table, to show their relations for this design case.

6.2. Circular design evaluation

6.2.1. Circular strategies

<i>Circular strategy</i>	<i>Design considerations</i>
<i>Long life</i>	Physical durability; Moretti is careful about quality and aims to create long lasting products. All products are tested & certified on mechanical and chemical performance. The product should have an aesthetic long life by using light colors and traditional/simple shapes which are less sensitive to fashion changes.
<i>Lifetime extension</i>	Reuse: the same product can be used by other users. For children's bedroom furniture this can mean re-using furniture by younger kids in a family. The furniture set is designed to be disassembled, allowing for reconfiguration of standard elements.
<i>Product recovery</i>	Parts harvesting: recovering elements and parts of returned items for reuse in other furniture.
<i>Material recycling</i>	The furniture is made of recycled wood and can be recycled entirely, being made of wood particles, glue and PPL edges But in the lifecycle, recycling is postponed as long as possible by prioritising on product level recovery and lifetime extension strategies.

6.2.2. Design aspects

Table 13 Design aspects implemented in the furniture demonstrator case

<i>Design aspect</i>	<i>Implementation</i>
<i>Accessibility</i>	(Cubic) elements and parts thereof are accessible and can be disassembled for reuse in another configuration.
<i>Adaptability</i>	Cube design & assembly system enables reconfiguration of the furniture
<i>Dis-&reassembly</i>	The cubes will be connected to each other with simple systems that anyone can disassemble and reassemble. The possibility of disassembly and re-assembly is guaranteed by the utilization of removable screws and gluing systems.
<i>Ergonomics</i>	Ergonomic considerations for the furniture include safety, comfort and reducing wear, table tested according to UNI EN 12521: 2016 The design was adapted for user needs; backrest comfort of the seat and headboard lining of the bed.

<i>Fault isolation</i>	All furniture should be made to avoid breakages and injuries, these requirements are stated by regulatory boards and duly reported in international technical standards for furniture products
<i>Interchangeability</i>	Individual, standard sized panels can be replaced and exchanged between furniture pieces.
<i>Simplification</i>	Using simple shapes and colours is expected to reduce the sensitivity to fashion changes. The current design complies to that vision, but could be improved to appeal to customers.
<i>Connection selection</i>	The possibility of disassembly and re-assembly is guaranteed by the utilization of removable screws and eliminating gluing systems. The fastener selection changed from plastic to metal for reasons of aesthetics, mechanical resistance, usability by common users and reusability (Figure 5)
<i>Material selection</i>	Panels are made of 100% recycled post-consumer wood such as furniture and packaging materials. At the end of their life they can be recycled entirely, being made of wood particles, glue and PPL edges. Melamine surface can be co-processed Formaldehyde-free particle board to facilitate recycling; it improves the recycle quality (but not recycled content % per se)
<i>Manufacturing</i>	Standardisation of the assemblies & thereby manufacturing process
<i>Modularity</i>	The products are composed by two different typologies of cube and they can have different destination of use. However, the initial cube models had to be adjusted for ergonomic reasons. The layout now includes two typologies, times two dimensions.
<i>Sacrificial elements</i>	Wear strips on edges to prevent wear on particle board
<i>Structural design</i>	All products dimensioned to be safe to use & opening opportunity for reuse due to good part condition
<i>Surface treatment selection</i>	The good quality of surface, i.e. coating & covers, prevents damages (scratches, stains, etc.) thus ensuring a longer life cycle. Light colors, not susceptible to trends, neutral colours such as scales of white and grey
<i>Documentation</i>	Technical Data Sheets, use instructions, maintenance and care instructions provided to end user The label developed by Cosmob gives a Circularity score based on material balance. This certification is given to a range of companies working with cosmob (Figure 6)
<i>Identification</i>	QR codes attached to product, linking to stakeholder platform. These are important for Moretti to track the furniture location & need for substitution.
<i>Monitoring</i>	The quality of the product is not directly monitored, but location & state are for support and logistics
<i>Standardisation</i>	Individual, standard sized panels can be replaced Standardisation of the panel dimensions for use in various types of furniture, facilitating standardisation in manufacturing and exchanging parts

Figure 4 Connection selection to enable dis- & reassembly, reconfiguration and interchangeability of parts.

Figure 5 labelling and certification of circularity measurement

6.2.3. Product specific aspects and strategies

Circular narrative, circular storytelling

Convey to the user that the product can be reconfigured and adapted to their changing desires. The message can be delivered in text, providing a design guide or user manual, image, showing some examples on the packaging, or through use-cues, where the product design shows how it can be used. For the latter, think of Lego bricks, which design shows it can be stacked to desire.

Material variability

To demonstrate the full circular potential of the product, it should be made using recycled material. A design challenge, which could create a nice visual cue to the circularity of the product, is how to work with variations in material supply.

Traceability & control

Degraded panels can be recycled through existing centralised channels.

Collaboration

Moretti notes that they aspire a takeback system like IKEA's. However, they operate on a much smaller scale, which makes it difficult. We propose to enter in an agreement with other furniture manufacturers to enable reuse of each other's panels. Such a collaborative effort could counterbalance the company scale.

Moretti

Figure 6 Demonstrator annotated with design aspects, colour coded by circular strategy.

6.3. Circular product design framework

6.3.1. Framework connections

Table 14 Circular product design strategy framework, connections between circular strategies and design aspects for this demonstrator highlighted in green

Design aim	Product integrity			Materials integrity	
	Long life	Lifetime extension	Product recovery	Structural reuse	Material recycling
Concept design					
Accessibility					
Adaptability					
Dis-&reassembly					
Ergonomics					
Fault isolation					
Functional packaging					
Interchangeability					
Simplification					
Embodiment					
Connection selection					
Material selection					
Manufacturing					
Modularity					
Sacrificial elements					
Structural design					
Surface treatment selection					
Detail design					
Documentation					
Identification					
Monitoring					
Standardisation					

6.3.2. Implementation in design process

The circular product design framework was mostly used as checklist. The existing product was analysed using the circular strategies and design aspects, to identify missing elements. This also supported decision making on where the design efforts should be focused on. The final design and prototype were also evaluated using the framework. Thus, the framework was found to provide a good introduction to implementing circular design considerations in product development, and useful for analysis and final evaluation of the designed demonstrator objects. This was supported by the layout of the framework.

The circular product design framework was considered to be well-structured. The left-to-right listing of circular strategies communicates a visual hierarchy, where indeed long life strategies are favoured over recycling. It also brings a clear distinction between strategies and design aspects; which respectively set a goal and provide a “how to” for the design process. For both strategies and design aspects, the framework provided a comprehensive overview.

7. Automotive: MAIER

7.1. Product redesign

7.1.1. Product description

MAIER redeveloped a dashboard fascia, with the aim to increase the recycled material content of the part. The Ecobulk redesign of the dashboard component is a recycled 2k injection moulded part, with fibre backing and aesthetic front. This design leverages the strength of secondary fibre reinforced plastics to compensate for the lower strength of recycled PC+ABS.

Automotive industry's recovery efforts are directed by the ELV directive. This stipulates recycling percentages for the complete vehicle, including the interior parts. This has shaped the recovery pathway for car parts; except for some distinctive (large and valuable) parts, the main focus is on recycling. To comply to this directives and industry context, MAIER chose to increase the use of recycled content in the demonstrator part. This allows reuse of reclaimed material, while accomodating the currently existing recycling and recovery processes. Incorporating recycled content in such (visual) components brought challenges to manufacturing and design.

This chapter starts by listing the circular strategies and design aspects for the construction demonstrator. These observations are annotated to pictures of the dashboard fascia, to put them into context, and brought together in a framework table to show interrelations between strategies and design aspects.

7.2. Circular design evaluation

7.2.1. Circular strategies

The lifecycle of the complete product, the car, is leading and defined by the car manufacturer. Individual parts, like the dashboard fascia, have to facilitate that lifecycle with major emphasis on recyclability on end of life. Requirements on the part concern durability, robustness in use and resistance to wear and environmental exposure. The assembly has to allow for repairs & maintenance done to the car.

Table 15 Circular strategies selected for the dashboard fascia automotive demonstrator case

<i>Circular strategy</i>	<i>Implementation</i>
<i>Physical durability</i>	The durability of the component depends mainly on the resistance (light, chemical, abrasion) of the aesthetic surface finishes.
<i>Recycling</i>	<p>Possibility of improving the use of recycled materials (on back side of the component).</p> <p>Recyclability is mandatory from the ELV directive.</p> <p>Recyclate sourcing is bound to policy as well. Many countries state that only locally recycled materials can be used in locally produced cars. This makes logistics, quality testing and production difficult. Moreover, different materials for different markets implies duplicating costs.</p> <p>Also, the legal limits on waste transfer obstructs sourcing recycled materials.</p>

7.2.2. Design aspects

The design of automotive components is highly standardised and governed by many requirements and regulations. The general design specifications are provided by the car manufacturer and MAIER can detail those. Still, materials, connections and packaging have to be selected from homologated lists. This concerns all parts of a car. Documentation is kept according to standards provided by the car maker and regulatory bodies to guarantee quality and traceability of the whole process. The parts have to comply to standards set by the automotive industry and defined by e.g. ISO, as well as regulatory bodies such as the EU. These requirements differ across geographic areas and car makers. Overall, these standards limit the freedom the design can afford in the development of new parts. These restrictions are all kept in mind for development of the demonstrator product by MAIER.

Table 16 Design aspects selected for the dashboard fascia automotive demonstrator case

<i>Design aspect</i>	<i>Implementation</i>
<i>Accessibility</i>	Allows accessibility to mounted parts such as the display
<i>Cleanability</i>	The part will be cleaned and has to withstand that.
<i>Dis-&reassembly</i>	According to current specifications from the automotive sector, the component must be designed to allow the easy Dis+Re-Assembly operations for the maintenance operations and at the End of Life of the vehicle. Allows accessibility to mounted parts such as the display
<i>Connection selection</i>	The parts of component are joined by snap-fits, which are integrated and moulded together with the part.
<i>Function integration</i>	Easier Assembly/Disassembly operations due to the reduction of parts for a multi-functional component; fasteners and structural frame are integrated with fascia and moulded in one piece. This also reduces the number of materials in the assembly as a whole.
<i>Material selection</i>	2K injection molding allows to increase the use of recycled materials. Virgin materials on the front, where a high level of aesthetic finishing is needed, and recycled material on the back. The process of 2k injection moulding requires compatible materials.
<i>Manufacturing</i>	2k injection moulding was used to increase recycle content. Recycled material is only usable for back frame due to its appearance. The process needs chemical compatible materials and tailoring to accommodate the recycled material (Figure 8) The design allows for different configurations of the fascia part: e.g. with GPS screen, only radio, or none of those installed. This is done using removable inserts in the mould.
<i>Modularity</i>	The manufacturing process is regarded modular, as it allows for configurable parts.
<i>Structural design</i>	The design combines aesthetics with structural requirements on stiffness, impact strength, support of electronic devices (loads), toughness, thermal stability and more. These requirements are validated with CAE tools and prototypes.
<i>Surface treatments</i>	Coatings, usually 2 or 3 layers of paint, are applied to protect the part from wear, ageing and chemical agents. The aesthetic appearance is regarded as the "last functionality" to be added.
<i>Identification</i>	Identification marks are compulsory: parts mark materials using symbols according to standards by ISO or car makers. In case of 2 materials, both are marked according to ISO, i.e. ABS/PLA represents a single part composed of two distinct materials ABS+PLA represents a blend, a compound of two materials
<i>Documentation</i>	Documentation is kept according to standards provide by the car maker and regulatory bodies such as the EU to guarantee quality and traceability of the whole process. Detailed documentation available between car makers & producers. TDS and MSDS are publicly available for risk assessment of processing, e.g. REACH.
<i>Standardisation</i>	The automotive sector is very standardised, regularised and these differ across countries and geographic areas. A car and all its constituting parts have to be completely homologated to be approved for road-use.

Figure 7 Examples of manufacturing defects on the parts

7.2.3. Product specific strategies and aspects

Physical durability

MAIER puts extra attention to the physical durability of the product. All parts have to comply to a range of testing standards, which are more extensively described in reports D2.1 and D2.3. This includes testing on: heat ageing, impact resistance, light resistance and wear by rubbing, dry abrasion or exposure to (sea) water, perspiration and hand cream. The parts is also subjected to 1 m. height drop tests as shown below.

Figure 8 clips and corners broke for some parts in the 1m drop test

Desirability

Use in car interiors bring specific requirements on aesthetics, for visible appearance, as well as odour. The natural fibre parts gave unexpected odours (coffee and vanilla-like) and were deemed unsuitable for use in interior parts, especially ventilation ducts etc.

Maier

Figure 9 Demonstrator annotated with design aspects, colour coded by circular strategy.

7.3. Circular product design framework

7.3.1. Framework connections

Table 17 Circular product design strategy framework, connections between circular strategies and design aspects for this demonstrator highlighted in green

Design aim	Product integrity			Materials integrity	
Circular strategy	Long life	Lifetime extension	Product recovery	Structural reuse	Material recycling
Accessibility					
Cleanability					
Dis-&reassembly					
Connection selection					
Function integration					
Material selection					
Manufacturing					
Modularity					
Structural design					
Surface treatments					
Identification					
Standardisation					

7.3.2. Implementation in design process

The developed prototype demonstrates the potential of reusing recycled material in car interiors. MAIER aims to expand this to more complex parts, such as front trim and door panels. These parts integrate more function and materials, and also more technical materials than the plastics used in this demonstrator. It is expected that the 2K process can be used for further implementation of recycled materials in car components, with designs developed according to the CE concept.

Project Ecobulk was the first time MAIER engaged in circular economy activities, and as such the designers had no specific background in circular product design. However, during the project, it was found that the circular design principles connected to already existing and well-known eco-design practices. The technological concepts are the same, but circular economy provided a different framing to the design goal; closing resource cycles rather than reducing environmental impact. Thus, while the framing of the circular economy was new, the design built on existing practices and technological background in the company.

Terminology however, was found to be confusing. In general, MAIER considers the materials used for internal car parts to be plastic compounds rather than composite materials. It was also found that the CE concept built mostly on academic perspectives and lacked grounding in industry and engineering practice. Over the course of the project, these definitions of terms and concepts were clarified and agreed upon. Thus, for further dissemination it is important to consider terminology with respect to various industry and academic contexts.

8. Automotive: Microcab

8.1. Product redesign

Microcab redesigned the switchpack housing, which is a central component of the car dashboard. It is an interesting design case, as it integrates a number of parts and functions. The subassembly contains mechanical, electronic, structural and aesthetic parts. Parts like switches and LED's are sourced from external suppliers, while the subframe and housing are developed in-house. The switchpack housing, developed in project Ecobulk, serves to assembly and protect these parts. This combination of various parts, functions and materials makes the switchpack an interesting and challenging design case for using circular materials in an automotive context.

The design paid attention to the lifespan and recovery pathways of the different materials and parts. Recycling electronic components is generally considered to be problematic. And thus, the housing was designed to protect these elements and give them a long lifespan. Given the expected level of use and environmental degradation, UV in particular, the housing will be replaced in 7-year refurbishment cycles. In these cycles, the housings will be removed and reprocessed into new interior parts.

This chapter starts by listing the circular strategies and design aspects for the construction demonstrator. These observations are annotated to pictures of the switchpack assembly, to put them into context, and brought together in a framework table to show interrelations between strategies and design aspects.

8.2. Circular design evaluation

8.2.1. Circular strategies

<i>Circular strategy</i>	<i>Implementation</i>
<i>Long life</i>	The life of the component itself is not prolonged, instead Microcab aims to extend material lifetime through planned reprocessing cycles. Also, the ability to replace the component supports a longer life (and creation of higher value) for the vehicle as a whole.
<i>Lifetime extension</i>	Maintenance: wear and tear for leased vehicles is greater than single owner owned vehicles. This is both because of the intensity of use for leased vehicles and because there is a tendency towards less care being taken for assets when they are not owned. Being able to remove and replace interior components will ensure that both functionally and aesthetically the interior of the vehicle will be maintained,
<i>Product recovery</i>	Microcab aims for refurbishing of the car interior at predefined time-intervals. This required matching up lifecycles & expected lifespans of the modules and materials used.
<i>Material recycling</i>	The switchpack housing is not expected to exceed the 7-year refurbishment cycles due to exposure to use & environmental conditions. Therefore, the housing will be recycled into new housings at these intervals, thereby preserving the materials.

8.2.2. Design aspects

Table 18 Design aspects implemented in the automotive-switchpack demonstrator case

<i>Design aspect</i>	<i>Implementation</i>
<i>Accessibility</i>	The front cover is easy to dismantle, exposing internal components for service if needed. Easy disassembly of the covers facilitates removal for reprocessing.
<i>Dis-&reassembly</i>	The switchpack assembly is designed to be easily disassembled to retrieve housing parts for recycling, or provide access to internal components for repairs where needed. Necessary for refurbishment, maintenance and repair operations The housing is separated from the screen, so there is no need to disassemble the screen as well. Clean disassembly to promote pure materials for recycling
<i>Interchangeability</i>	The switchpack assembly as a whole is a self-contained unit that can be interchanged for service, or even be exchanged between current and future Microcab car models.
<i>Connection selection</i>	Just one type of fastener is used in the switchpack assembly to ease disassembly.
<i>Function integration</i>	The Switchpack housing holds parts together with minimal interventions (number of connections and fasteners needed).
<i>Material selection</i>	Reduced the number of material types in the interior to facilitate collection, concentration and reprocessing of material batches. Thermoplastic material rather than thermoset composite to enable recycling.
<i>Manufacturing</i>	The tooling is adaptable, which makes it possible to change the switch layout in future revisions. The narrow manufacturing tolerances make for a snug fit of components, reducing the number of connections needed.
<i>Modularity</i>	The grouping of materials and parts is one of the key drivers in the design. The module composition is governed by the type of exposure & materials used, in order to achieve components of equal lifetime and thereby service intervals.
<i>Sacrificial elements</i>	The switchpack housing protects internal, non-circular, parts to prolong their lifetime. The housing itself will be replaced in 7-year refurbishment intervals.
<i>Structural design</i>	The fibre length will decrease in successive reprocessing cycles, but fibre length is not critical, as the housing is not a structural part.
<i>Surface treatments</i>	No additional surface coatings have been added, displaying the natural fibre reinforced material and showcasing the "Eco-ness" of the material
<i>Identification</i>	For small series, as the current Vianova, identification based on vehicle serial no.'s is still possible, since this has relatively small chains of manufacturer and users in leasing & sharing schemes.
<i>Monitoring</i>	The housing quality will be checked through visual inspections while in service.
<i>Standardisation</i>	Same unit is (re)usable across various cars.

8.2.3. Product specific strategies & design aspects

Circular narrative, circular storytelling

Biobased and recycled materials have a distinctive appearance, compared to virgin plastics. Such as colour fluctuations and visibility of the embedded reinforcement fibres. Microcab appreciates this, and intends to leave the interior parts uncoated. Showing the material's composition will communicate the "eco-ness" of the design to the user. As such, the aesthetics of the switchpack, and other interior components, play a role in telling the circular story of the car to its users.

Timing, planning and roadmaps

Microcab proposed to use the same material for parts with a similar lifespan. This relates to the design rules for modularity, which suggests to group parts in a subassembly based on a matching property [77]. Grouping components based on lifespan, and assigning the same materials to those, will have benefits in managing the return flow and acquiring material volumes for re-processing. Microcab developed posters visualizing the part lifetimes and considers matching the materials composition of parts accordingly.

Figure 10 Lifecycle planning posters developed by Microcab, showing the lifetime extension activities of the interior (left) and complete vehicle (right)

Figure 11 Demonstrator annotated with design aspects, colour coded by circular strategy.

8.3. Circular product design framework

8.3.1. Framework connections

Table 19 Circular product design strategy framework, connections between circular strategies and design aspects for this demonstrator highlighted in green

Design aspects	Circular strategy				
	Long life	Lifetime extension	Product recovery	Structural reuse	Material recycling
Accessibility					
Dis-&reassembly					
Interchangeability					
Connection selection					
Function integration					
Material selection					
Manufacturing					
Modularity					
Sacrificial elements					
Structural design					
Surface treatments					
Identification					
Monitoring					
Standardisation					

8.3.2. Implementation in design process

The circular product design framework was deemed usable in this design project. The framework lists a comprehensive set of design aspects for a circular product which helps the designer to locate problems in the design, and points out specific areas that need further attention. Also, it highlights other opportunities for circular product design. Thus, the framework can serve as a checklist to evaluate a design, or signal additional opportunities.

To develop a circular product, the designer has to understand all options and select those that are appropriate. The framework presents a holistic approach to product design, listing strategies and design aspects. This listing supports selection of which strategy to focus on, and creates an understanding of relations between strategies. In this way, it helps to structure the product development process.

To further improve the product, and for development of similar products, it is necessary to consider the wider supply chain. Product assemblies like the switchpack are a combination of off-the-shelf components bought from external suppliers, and parts developed in-house. All stakeholders have their role in constructing a fully circular supply chain. And if constructed well, everyone benefits. But, as was noted during the interview, "it doesn't work if one of them is still linear". Stakeholder collaboration is thus an important aspect of circular product development.

9. Automotive: CRF

9.1. Product redesign

9.1.1. Product description

CRF demonstrated use of “green materials” a dashboard component. Since the lifecycle of the interior parts is dictated by that of the vehicle as a whole, product longevity strategies were considered out of scope for this project. Instead, CRF focused on increasing the use of “green materials” the demonstrator case. CRF considers recycled and biobased sources for these “green materials”, to lower the impact of the produced parts.

Recycled materials and biobased materials can usually not be used for such components, as they do not meet the required standards. This limits the uptake of recycled and biobased content in interior manufacturing, but also obstructs closing the loop. 1:1 recycling, where interior recycle would be used to produce new interior parts is considered infeasible. As result, these components are usually downcycled in a cascading system. While this typically results in low-grade commodity goods being made of the recycle, CRF envisions cascading within the vehicle:

- First lifecycle: dashboard part - high visual quality required
- Second lifecycle: airduct
- Third lifecycle: “under the hood” part, like wheelcovers
- Fourth lifecycle: carpets etc.

CRF demonstrated use of biobased and recycled materials on the dashboard component. The original component shape will remain largely unchanged, using the same type of connections. But the manufacturing process and materials changed; CRF produces components using compounds delivered by Tecnaro (biobased plastics) and Coventive (carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic pellets).

This chapter starts by listing the circular strategies and design aspects for this demonstrator. These observations are annotated to pictures of the dashboard, to put them into context, and brought together in a framework table to show interrelations between strategies and design aspects.

9.2. Circular design evaluation

9.2.1. Circular strategies

Table 20 Circular strategies selected for the CRF demonstrator case

<i>Circular strategy</i>	<i>Implementation</i>
<i>Long life</i>	Durability, robustness in use, and resistance to everyday wear. This means resistance to scratching, cleaning & exposure to environmental & use conditions
<i>Lifetime extension</i>	The part allows for and facilitates repairs & maintenance done to the car.
<i>Product recovery</i>	Recovery of individual parts and reuse of the component has been considered. This can be done if a dismantler disassembles the complete car, but this is common. Disassembly is only done for valuable or important components such as doors or bumpers, small parts like this are not recovered. As such, the current EoL management doesn't allow for reuse of components and complete dismantling is not expected to be applied on short notice.
<i>Material recycling</i>	The product is recyclable and made using recycled materials.

9.2.2. Design aspects

Table 21 Design aspects selected for the CRF demonstrator case

<i>Design aspect</i>	<i>Implementation</i>
<i>Accessibility</i>	Underlying parts are accessible for repair by removing the cover manually.
<i>Cleanability</i>	The part can only be damaged by chemical substances; impact damage is unlikely in its mounted position. It has been tested to withstand expected use conditions such as solar radiation/UV exposure as in EU (Americas have higher requirements), and resistance to wear (scratch & mar). As well as exposure to (everyday) chemical substances, such as lotions & foods.
<i>Dis-&reassembly</i>	Part can be (mechanically & manually) separated from the dashboard to allow for, facilitate repairs & maintenance done to the car.
<i>Connection selection</i>	The cover is fixed with (Polyamide) clips which fit onto the rectangular holed mounts on the rear. These clips are selected to meet requirements from the assembly line (Figure 12). Part can be (mechanically & manually) separated from the dashboard.
<i>Function integration</i>	Connections and keying elements are integrated with the part (injection moulded in one piece)
<i>Keying</i>	Alignment pins at the bottom assist mounting of the part, the overall shape makes that it can only be positioned in one way (poka yoke).
<i>Material selection</i>	Materials selected to withstand expected exposure & use conditions Biobased (renewable) and recyclable materials used. Scratches were less visible on PLA grades, but more so on PP
<i>Manufacturing</i>	If the recyclate properties are lower than 90% compared to virgin material, the design has to be adapted to counter the reduction in mechanical properties, for example by increasing wall thickness. This means that the moulds as well as the process parameters (time, temperature etc) for manufacturing the parts have to be adjusted. In practice, this means recycled materials can only be used in new products, not as drop-in replacement in existing production.
<i>Sacrificial elements</i>	The clips get destroyed in disassembly, but part remains intact.
<i>Structural design</i>	Couldn't use recyclate as the part dimensions were not variable.
<i>Surface treatments</i>	The Ecobulk part has a fine surface texture. The PLA compount performs best on UV resistance & scratch & mar, the PP-jute is more sensitive
<i>Identification</i>	The part is marked using ISO symbols.
<i>Standardisation</i>	Connections are highly standardised in automotive, i.e. one type of clip is used in the complete assembly line of the interior. CRF deliberately diverts from standardised material formulations. Does this hamper or facilitate recycling? It could hamper due to the foreign materials & incompatibility, it could facilitate because of its composition & the recyclability of the material.

Figure 12 Connection selection: mounting using clips

Materials selection

CRF noted that using recycled materials results in approximately 10% cost savings. Post-consumer plastics however, are of lower quality than virgin materials. The design can be adapted to counter the reduction in mechanical properties, for example by increasing wall thickness. This means that the moulds for manufacturing the parts have to be adjusted. In practice, this means these recycled materials can only be used in new products, not as drop-in replacement in existing production. Thus, the demonstrator did not focus on reuse of recycled plastics, but rather on using biobased materials.

Table 22 Demonstrator products manufactured using bio-based reinforced plastics

9.3. Product specific strategies and design

Physical durability: Environmental stability

CRF puts extra attention to the physical durability of the product. All parts have to comply to a range of testing standards, which are more extensively described in reports D2.1 and D2.3. This includes testing on: Scratching, marring (point load impression), heat deflection and resistance to exposing the material to UV and an range of chemical substances. These substances can be of everyday use, such as ketchup and hand lotions. The degree of required resistivity depends on the location in the car interior, as shown for UV exposure in the figure below. The dashboard fascia were tested at 225 kJ/m². SAE J2412 tests showed that the PLA could be used in low area, PP in medium exposed areas.

Figure 13 UV resistance areas, ecobulk part tested on 225 kJ/m².

1240 kJ/m² – Green

Instrument panel horizontal surfaces

601 kJ/m² - Yellow

Upper pillar trim, instrument panel vertical surfaces, package tray & door roll-over trim materials.

225 kJ/m² - Blue, lower

Seating trim, door trim, floor console, lower pillar / cowl trim, overhead console / trim materials

112,5 kJ/m²

Carpets, trunk, doors sill trims

CRF

Figure 14 Demonstrator annotated with design aspects, colour coded by circular strategy.

9.4. Circular product design framework

9.4.1. Framework connections

Table 23 Circular product design strategy framework, connections between circular strategies and design aspects for this demonstrator highlighted in green

Design aim	Product integrity			Materials integrity	
	Long life	Lifetime extension	Product recovery	Structural reuse	Material recycling
Accessibility					
Cleanability					
Dis-&reassembly					
Connection selection					
Function integration					
Keying					
Material selection					
Manufacturing					
Sacrificial elements					
Structural design					
Identification					
Standardisation					

9.4.2. Implementation in design process

The design strategy framework aligned with the design goals for CRF. CRF aims to use increase the use of green materials in car interiors. This can be recycled, or biobased materials. CRF explored both directions in the context of Ecobulk, and this activity fitted with the design aspects provided in the framework. But, it was also found that circular product design requires re-thinking of the design process.

Circular product design requires interaction with multiple stakeholders, to close the resource loop for the product. Such collaboration was represented in the Ecobulk project by having conversations with stakeholders from the value chain and co-developing the demonstrator. Still, it must be noted that cars themselves are a complex assembly of parts and material, where different stakeholders come into play. These are external stakeholders, such as the collaboration between material suppliers (Coventive, Tecnar) and the car maker (CRF). But also internal stakeholders, such as the various departments within the company, addressing for example the materials selection of the car interior, under the hood, or exterior parts. The extent and complexity of the product assembly, reflected in the number of stakeholders, can make changes of direction challenging.

Interactions with internal and external stakeholders signal the need for a common language and shared goals. CRF regards the circular product framework usable to stimulate discussions between stakeholders & departments in the organisation.

10. Student design projects

Ten students of Industrial Design Engineering, TU Delft, were tasked with the redesign of furniture. The assignment was based on the case of circular furniture in Ecobulk, providing the following boundary conditions:

- Construct furniture using particle board, taking the material's strengths and weaknesses into account
- Demonstrate circular furniture can be made out of this material, following a circular strategy of choice
- Make sure the concept is 'future proof', regarding trends, style and adaptability

Students were given a preliminary circular product design framework for composites, access to the fastener finder (developed in D2.5) and background information on Ecobulk and the context of circular furniture. In addition, a local woodworker was visited to get first-hand information on working with particle board.

The design project ran for one semester and the group was coached by two lecturers on a weekly basis. Bram van der Grinten (researcher) and Jelle Joustra (PhD candidate) acted as clients in on behalf of Ecobulk and the Circular Product Design research group.

The following paragraphs provide a brief description of the developed concepts. Each description is accompanied by a presentation poster, visualising the product proposal. The design aspects are given for each case individually, to directly relate them to the design case. The second chapter evaluates the Circular strategies and the circular product design framework for composites.

10.1. Product redesigns & Design aspects

10.1.1. Fairbinding

In *Fairbinding*, the designer immediately focused on ensuring long product life. The concept was further refined through material experiments, learning the particle board's strengths and weaknesses, and by further defining the target group (starters on the housing market). In the embodiment, the designer collected insights on fastener systems through catalogues, experts and prototyping, which were used to develop a new connector system.

Table 24 Design aspects implemented in the Fairbinding design case

<i>Design aspects</i>	<i>Lifetime extension implementation</i>
<i>Adaptability</i>	The furniture was designed to be adaptable in use, by changing the overall layout and function.
<i>Dis-&reassembly</i>	To achieve the goal of adaptable furniture, it had to allow for dis and reassembly.
<i>Ergonomics</i>	The furniture can be (dis) assembled using a single tool.
<i>Interchangeability</i>	All parts are interchangeable to facilitate repairs & adaptations.
<i>Simplification</i>	The assembly structure and process was developed to be easy to understand, not needing a manual.
<i>Connection selection</i>	Developed a new type of connection to facilitate adaptability of the furniture. The connector was developed using many prototypes and small tests.
<i>Keying</i>	The developed connector has keying features to support positioning and assembly
<i>Material selection</i>	The material was stated by the design assignment, focusing on particle board. The potential of the material was explored through early stage prototyping. Experimenting with the material led to insights as to where the limitations and weaknesses were to be found. In the case of particle board: the edges that crumble in manufacturing or get damaged in-use. The connection piece is made of aluminium, to be strong, corrosion resistant and recyclable.
<i>Modularity</i>	The parts connect in modules, which can be assembled into different types of furniture.
<i>Structural design</i>	The 45° angles on the panels reduced the number of parts needed. Sharp edges (45°) were avoided as these are more vulnerable to damage.
<i>Standardisation</i>	Panel dimensions were chosen to maximise the reconfigurability of the system, but minimise the variety in parts. This makes it easier to exchange and reconfigure parts.

10.1.2. The furniture library

The *Furniture library* aims to exploit the gap between use cycles, building on an existing furniture line. IKEA was selected as target company. Through interviews and portfolio analysis, the designer noticed the variety of fastener and connections systems, despite IKEA's efforts to minimise those and introduce standard parts. The *Furniture library* provides bookcase elements (walls, shelves) systematic sizing system, to warrant optimal adaptability of the furniture.

Table 25 Design aspects implemented in the Furniture library design case

<i>Design aspects</i>	<i>Lifetime extension implementation</i>
<i>Adaptability</i>	The furniture library allows users to adapt the furniture in an easy way
<i>Dis-&reassembly</i>	The parts can be disassembled to allow exchange
<i>Interchangeability</i>	Interchangeable parts enable exchange through the furniture library and adapting the furniture to the user's needs
<i>Keying</i>	wedge-dowel connections
<i>Manufacturing</i>	The board on frame panels reduce material usage, but do require a specific fabrication process and do not allow for adjustments at a later stage, such a replacing the top layer or re-sizing the board.
<i>Modularity</i>	The whole furniture system is modular and allows for replacement and interchangeability of parts.
<i>Surface treatment selection</i>	Replacing the top-layer of a board-on-frame panel is impossible, since the skin layer is integral element of the board construction
<i>Standardisation</i>	Built on the sizing system for panels of IKEA's PLATSA series to facilitate exchange

10.1.3. Rödtråd

Rödtråd is a furniture system that allows for reconfiguration of the table, bookcase and bed. The designer envisioned a comprehensive approach on circular furniture; starting from a business model (canvas) rather than zooming in on recovery of a specific part. This resulted in a new design and user story. The "red thread" symbolises the product journey and keeps the product assembly together.

Or, as the designer put it: "Rödtråd is a Swedish expression that means 'a theme that keeps recurring within a storyline and connects all events'. The philosophy behind my design is that it will be the recurring theme in circular furniture design. It is a line of furniture with respect for its own materials. The connection with the thread no longer damages the materials but works together to create a trustworthy system. Using one, overarching idea.

Table 26 Design aspects implemented in the Rödtråd design case

Design aspects	Lifetime extension implementation
Adaptability	The furniture can be adjusted to ensure furniture fits various interiors & locations (e.g. under stairs)
Interchangeability	The parts can be exchanged between furniture types to support reconfiguration and adapting the furniture.
Simplification	The dis- & reassembly sequence needs to be simple to stimulate users actually doing it
Connection selection	The "red thread" symbolises the product journey and keeps the product together
Function integration	Was noted to not always the best way forward; more integration can make separation of materials more complex
Manufacturing	Manufacturability, especially of new fastener and connection types was checked with quick prototypes.
Modularity	The parts can be exchanged between furniture types to allow for interchanging (between furniture) or exchange (with new parts)
Identification	Relates to documentation and ties into ikea's user history retention; ikea could recognise the furniture if your future family returns it 20 years from now.
Monitoring	The return system will show which parts are prone to break or last for long, and thus give designers insight into product use and wear.
Standardisation	Regarded as usable means to create a product that can be disassembled in a simple way by the user

10.1.4. Chameleon

Chameleon

- Hoogte verstelbaar
- Zit en Sta bureau
- Volledig reviseerbaar
- Vervangbare toplaag

Business plan

- Lease: 60 euro per jaar
- Installatie en ophalen
- Recycling partners
- Logistieke partners

The *Chameleon* concept integrated a number of circular strategies, but emphasized on product recovery. The *Chameleon* aims for a furniture leasing system for large offices. Early in the project, the student went to interview a company with a large office space. He found out that the furniture is exchanged between departments, and that a service contract is in place to cover (premature) breakages. At end of life, it's sent to the recycling station. Knowing that some of the materials within a typical desk are not or hardly recyclable, he decided to prevent the need for recycling. This culminated in a desk that can be remanufactured and refurbished, to really become as-new to enable multiple use-cycles.

Table 27 Design aspects implemented in the Chameleon design case

<i>Design aspects</i>	<i>Lifetime extension implementation</i>
<i>Dis-&reassembly</i>	Designed for disassembly, to allow repairs and reuse of parts.
<i>Fault isolation</i>	The design is transparent and the construction clearly visible, which aids fault location and repairs
<i>Simplification</i>	Minimised the number of fasteners and assembly steps to facilitate handling.
<i>Connection selection</i>	Standard nuts & bolts are used, which enables easy disassembly, repairs, as well as reuse.
<i>Material selection</i>	Easy recyclable and reusable materials were used on the most wearing and prominent parts
<i>Modularity</i>	Parts are exchangeable, for example to change the desk appearance
<i>Sacrificial elements</i>	The desktop surface is meant to take most of the wear, and to be recycled when the desk is refurbished.
<i>Structural design</i>	Particle board was the starting point of the assignment, but has some drawbacks in durability. So, protective layers were added, and no holes drilled in the particle board. "keeping the particle board just a plain board". A protective frame was added
<i>Surface treatment selection</i>	The desktop layer is made of recyclable plastic, and the board-supporting frame is made of aluminium. Apply a new layer of (powder)coating to refurbish a metal parts, there's not always a need for recycling in such cases.
<i>Standardisation</i>	All aluminium profiles, board dimensions and fasteners are selected from standard parts.

10.1.5. GÜLIA

The *Gülia* system is based on an external connector for particleboard panels. External, to keep the panel intact and retain their value. The connectors come in 3 different layouts, allowing users to easily assemble, re-assemble and adapt the cabinet to their desires. The connector pieces are made of recycled plastic and available in four distinctive colours that meet the requirements of this material selection.

Together with an online planning tool, the *Gülia* system offers a versatile and affordable furniture piece, that through its modularity and ease of use invites users to both reconfigure the furniture, as well as discuss the circular economy.

The designer focused on the inner circles of the circular economy, preserving component quality and facilitating personalisation to maintain both physical and emotional value.

Table 28 Design aspects implemented in the Gülia design case

<i>Design aspects</i>	<i>Lifetime extension implementation</i>
<i>Adaptability</i>	Gülia allows users to change their interior without the need to buy new pieces. The appearance can be adapted by changing color and type of connection elementsd.
<i>Dis-&reassembly</i>	The cabinet can be easily dis- & reassembled by means of the proprietary connector elements
<i>Fault isolation</i>	Damaged parts can be isolated and exchanged.
<i>Connection selection</i>	Gülia developed a new connector type, which builds a cabinet without using screws. Screws were avoided as these damage the boards.
<i>Modularity</i>	First thing that came to mind when thinking about Circular design, often noted by coaches
<i>Documentation</i>	Assembly manual provided with the design proposal

10.2. Circular design evaluation

10.2.1. Circular strategies

All furniture concepts aimed to prolong the life of particle board panels, as these were deemed difficult to recycle. Panel longevity was mostly achieved through lifetime extension approaches, with a notable focus on reconfiguration, upgrades and adaptability. Structural reuse was recognised incidentally, but not further detailed. Recycling of particle board was postponed as much as possible and assumed to follow current practice. Special attention was given to make all other parts of the designs recyclable and, in some cases, made of recycled materials.

Most designers attempted to integrate multiple strategies into their concept. All agreed that achieving a long life was most desirable, and aimed to integrate those approaches with all other lifetime extension, product recovery, structural reuse and recycling approaches. In the course of the project however, they found that "it was very hard to integrate them all into one product" [*EcoJoint*]. This resulted in product-distinctive combinations; "You will end up in a sort of hybrid [product], where some parts need to be easy to recycle, while other parts are reused or repaired. The first part of the return process is similar (collection, inspection, disassembly), so why not distinguish between reuse and recycling then?" [*Chameleon*]. Thus complying to multiple circular strategies and integrating those into a single product concept was found to be possible to a limited extent.

Table 30 Circular strategies selected in the development of circular furniture by novice designers

<i>Circular strategy</i>	<i>Implementation</i>
<i>Long life</i>	Achieving a long product life is very psychological, as it has to address the human interaction with the product (system) [and was therefore not further detailed] [<i>Rödtråd</i>].
<i>Lifetime extension</i>	<p>Long life of the materials is achieved by making the product adaptable. All parts are exchangeable when damaged, to maintain the overall furniture value [<i>Fairbinding</i>].</p> <p>The goal was to make the furniture fully adaptable by the user, and thus prolong its lifetime. The furniture library provides parts and support for users to upgrade their furniture to their desires. [<i>Furniture library</i>].</p> <p><i>Rödtråd</i> is a line of furniture with respect for its own materials. The connection with the thread no longer damages the materials but works together to create a trustworthy system. Using one, overarching idea [<i>Rödtråd</i>].</p> <p>The connector blocks and planks allow for reuse and thereby extension of the product lifetime. The connectors are external and as such do not affect the panel's integrity. [<i>Gülia</i>]</p> <p>"if you make the connection from an endlessly recyclable materials and design it in a way that it fails before the particle board does, the particle board will not end up in landfill and the connection can be replaced easily and sustainably." [<i>Eco-Joint</i>]</p>

<i>Product recovery</i>	<p>Most of the frame is designed to last multiple use cycles, and should therefore have a long life. It can be remanufactured and refurbished, to really become as-new to successive users [<i>Chameleon</i>]</p> <p>Given little consideration because it requires development of return logistics and associated user journeys [<i>Rödtråd</i>].</p>
<i>Structural reuse</i>	<p>Potential way to reuse panel materials, but given little consideration because it requires development of return logistics and associated user journeys [<i>Rödtråd</i>].</p>
<i>Material recycling</i>	<p>The desk-top is designed to be replaced after each use cycle, given the damage and wear it has likely sustained, this part is subject to recycling. [<i>Chameleon</i>]</p> <p><i>Gülia</i> used recycled plastic for the connector blocks, and selected four distinctive colours that match the colour availability of recycled plastics. [<i>Gülia</i>]</p> <p>The fasteners are designed to facilitate separation and reprocessing. [<i>all concepts</i>]</p>

10.2.2. Case specific observations

Target group identification

To refine the assignment and develop a vision for product development, the students selected a target group. Often, this started with a generic use case and furniture type, e.g. office, domestic or hotel furniture, which was then progressively refined. Changes in the context, such as company reorganisations, moving house or reconfiguring hotel rooms then gave a starting point for developing the circular strategy and product vision. To make these target group considerations explicit, some students developed personas, while others remained at a case and context description.

Reinforced learning

Takeback of product post-use was seen to bring benefits for the manufacturer in terms of product improvement: returned products show use, abuse and damages. Such observations are useful for developing a new product, or upgrade.

10.3. Circular product design framework

10.3.1. Framework connections

Table 31 Circular product design strategy framework, connections between circular strategies and design aspects for these design cases highlighted in yellow

<i>Design aim</i>	Product integrity			Materials integrity	
<i>Circular strategy</i>	Long life	Lifetime extension	Product recovery	Structural reuse	Material recycling
<i>Concept design</i>					
Adaptability					
Dis-&reassembly					
Ergonomics					
Fault isolation					
Functional packaging					
Interchangeability					
Simplification					
<i>Embodiment</i>					
Connection selection					
Function integration					
Keying					
Material selection					
Manufacturing					
Modularity					
Sacrificial elements					
Structural design					
Surface treatment selection					
<i>Detail design</i>					
Documentation					
Identification					
Monitoring					
Standardisation					
<i>Circular storytelling</i>					

10.3.2. Implementation in design process.

Learning by doing

Most of the students did not have prior experience with the case material: particle board. To learn more about the material's properties and processing, they visited a furniture manufacturing workshop. In

addition, some students chose to get hands-on experience by working with the material in the faculty's model making workshop. These early prototyping activities provided insights, among which were the working of fastening systems, load introduction, surface finishes and edge protection. This led to design constraints such as "protect the surface from wear" [*Chameleon*], and ideas that were further developed in the project, such as new fastening systems [*Fairbinding*]. Thus, practical knowledge transfer and learning-by-doing were employed to fill the knowledge gap regarding material characteristics.

Implementation of design aspects

In the evaluation, students noticed the number of the design aspects used in the project. A number which they didn't expect, noting that it "*That it sort of went unnoticed*". Which they partially attributed to the strong relations between several design aspects.

Relations between design aspects

Some design aspects are closely interrelated. For example in the case of the Rödtråd concept development: the design goal of "Simplification of disassembly" (which already ties together two design aspects) was realised by means of standardisation. This resulted in modular, interchangeable parts and adaptable solutions. Afterwards, the designer reflected "although it was a design process, I did not need to design every step, some followed logically from what I already did". The same interconnectedness was observed in the other design cases. Despite these links, the design aspects should be addressed individually for the design case at hand. The designers objected to the idea of offering the connected design aspects as a "package solution". The manifestation of the design aspects and the specific connections were found to be case specific, and recognised as such by the designers.

11. Appendices

11.1. References

1. Ellen MacArthur Foundation Towards the Circular Economy 1: Economic and business rationale for an accelerated transition Available online: <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/publications/towards-the-circular-economy-vol-1-an-economic-and-business-rationale-for-an-accelerated-transition>.
2. Korhonen, J.; Honkasalo, A.; Seppälä, J. Circular Economy: The Concept and its Limitations. *Ecol. Econ.* **2018**, *143*, 37–46.
3. Balkenende, A.R.; Bocken, N.; Bakker, C.A. Design for the Circular Economy. In *The Routledge Handbook of Sustainable Design*; Egenhoefer, R.B., Ed.; Routledge International Handbooks, 2017; pp. 498–513 ISBN 978-1138650176.
4. Bakker, C.A.; Balkenende, A.R.; Poppelaars, F. Design for Product Integrity in a Circular Economy. In *Designing for the Circular Economy*; Charter, M., Ed.; Routledge International Handbooks, 2018 ISBN 9781138081017.
5. Bocken, N.; de Pauw, I.; Bakker, C.A.; van der Grinten, B. Product design and business model strategies for a circular economy. *J. Ind. Prod. Eng.* **2016**, *33*, 308–320.
6. Joustra, J.J.; Flipsen, S.F.; Balkenende, A.R. Circular Design of Composite Products : A Preliminary Framework Based on Insights from Literature and Industry. In Proceedings of the PLATE Product Lifetimes And The Environment 2019 – Conference Proceedings; Nissen, N.F., Jaeger-Erben, M., Eds.; TU Berlin University Press: Berlin, 2019.
7. Yang, Y.; Boom, R.; Irion, B.; van Heerden, D.J.; Kuiper, P.; de Wit, H. Recycling of composite materials. *Chem. Eng. Process. Process Intensif.* **2012**, *51*, 53–68.
8. Jensen, J.P.; Skelton, K. Wind turbine blade recycling: Experiences, challenges and possibilities in a circular economy. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2018**, *97*, 165–176.
9. Beauson, J.; Brøndsted, P. Wind turbine blades: an End of Life Perspective. In *MARE-WINT: New Materials and Reliability in Offshore Wind Turbine Technology*; Ostachowicz, W., McGugan, M., Schröder-Hinrichs, J.U., Luczak, M., Eds.; Springer, 2016; pp. 421–432 ISBN 9783319390956.
10. Nijssen, R.P.L. *Composite Materials*; 1st ed.; VKCN, 2015; Vol. 3; ISBN 978-90-77812-471.
11. Oliveux, G.; Dandy, L.O.; Leeke, G.A. Current status of recycling of fibre reinforced polymers: Review of technologies, reuse and resulting properties. *Prog. Mater. Sci.* **2015**, *72*, 61–99.
12. Mativenga, P.T.; Sultan, A.A.M.; Agwa-Ejon, J.; Mbohwa, C. Composites in a Circular Economy: A Study of United Kingdom and South Africa. *Procedia CIRP* **2017**, *61*, 691–696.
13. Zhang, J.; Chevali, V.S.; Wang, H.; Wang, C.H. Current status of carbon fibre and carbon fibre composites recycling. *Compos. Part B Eng.* **2020**, *193*, 108053.
14. European Parliament and Council 2000/53/EC on end-of-life vehicles. *Off. J. Eur. Union* **2000**, *L*, 34–42.
15. Cherrington, R.; Goodship, V.; Meredith, J.; Wood, B.M.; Coles, S.R.; Vuillaume, A.; Feito-Boirac, A.; Spee, F.; Kirwan, K. Producer responsibility: Defining the incentive for recycling composite wind turbine blades in Europe. *Energy Policy* **2012**, *47*, 13–21.
16. Longana, M.L.; Ong, N.; Yu, H.N.; Potter, K.D. Multiple closed loop recycling of carbon fibre composites with the HiPerDiF (High Performance Discontinuous Fibre) method. *Compos. Struct.* **2016**, *153*, 271–277.
17. Pickering, S.J.; Turner, T.A.; Meng, F.; Morris, C.N.; Heil, J.P.; Wong, K.H.; Melendi-Espina, S. Developments in the fluidised bed process for fibre recovery from thermoset composites. In Proceedings of the 2nd Annual Composites and Advanced Materials Expo, CAMX; 2015.
18. University of Delaware - Center for composite materials TuFF Available online: <https://www.ccm.udel.edu/research/program-highlights/tuff/> (accessed on May 19, 2021).

19. DecomTools Available online: <https://northsearegion.eu/decomtools/about/> (accessed on Oct 18, 2019).
20. Neowa Our contribution to a clean future: The neocomp project Available online: <https://www.neowa.de/en/references/neocomp-engl> (accessed on Jun 16, 2020).
21. Gen 2 Carbon (former ELG Carbon Fibre) Available online: <https://gen2carbon.com/> (accessed on May 19, 2021).
22. EcoBulk project Available online: www.ecobulk.eu (accessed on Dec 1, 2017).
23. FiberEUse project Available online: <http://www.fibereuse.eu/> (accessed on Jun 16, 2020).
24. Re-Wind project Available online: <https://www.re-wind.info/> (accessed on Jun 16, 2020).
25. Callister, W.; Rethwisch, D. *Materials science and engineering: an introduction*; 2007; ISBN 9780471736967.
26. Witten, E.; Sauer, M.; Kühnel, M. *Composites Market Report 2017*; 2017;
27. Ashby, M.F. *Materials Selection in Mechanical Design*; 3rd ed.; Elsevier Butterworth-Heinemann: Oxford, 2005; ISBN 0750661682.
28. Effing, M. Expert insights in Europe's booming composites market. *Reinf. Plast.* **2018**, *62*, 219–223.
29. Perry, N.; Bernard, A.; Laroche, F.; Pompidou, S. Improving design for recycling – Application to composites. *CIRP Ann.* **2012**, *61*, 151–154.
30. Grote, K.-H.; Fischer, N.; Schneider, U.; Co, I.; Engi, N.O.N.; Fo, P.D.; St, R.R.O.F.; With, R. Product design for recycling of structures with composite material. In Proceedings of the ICED : international conference on engineering design 11; Tampere University of Technology: Tampere, Finland, 1997; pp. 347–350.
31. Pahl, G.; Beitz, W.; Feldhusen, J.; Grote, K.H. *Engineering Design: A Systematic Approach*; Wallace, K., Blessing, L., Eds.; Third edit.; Springer: London, 2007; Vol. 11; ISBN 9781846283185.
32. Perry, N.; Pompidou, S.; Mantaux, O. Information exchanges between experts for thermoset composites design for recycling. *Int. J. Environ. Waste Manag.* **2014**, *13*, 396–411.
33. Butenko, V.; Wilwer, J.; Spadinger, M.; Albers, A. A qualitative study to identify the need and requirements on further development of design guidelines for fibre-reinforced composites. In Proceedings of the Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Engineering Design (ICED17); Vancouver, 2017; Vol. Resource-S, pp. 309–318.
34. Leahy, P.G. End-of-life Options for Composite Material Wind Turbine Blades: Recover, Repurpose or Reuse? In Proceedings of the 14th SWEDES Conference; Dubrovnik, 2019; pp. 1–9.
35. Bank, L.C.; Arias, F.R.; Yazdanbakhsh, A.; Gentry, T.R.; Al-Haddad, T.; Chen, J.F.; Morrow, R. Concepts for reusing composite materials from decommissioned wind turbine blades in affordable housing. *Recycling* **2018**, *3*.
36. Den Hollander, M. Design for managing obsolescence, Delft University of Technology, 2018.
37. Psomopoulos, C.S.; Kalkanis, K.; Kaminaris, S.; Ioannidis, G.C.; Pachos, P. A review of the potential for the recovery of wind turbine blade waste materials. *Recycling* **2019**, *4*, 1–9.
38. Ayre, D. Technology advancing polymers and polymer composites towards sustainability: A review. *Curr. Opin. Green Sustain. Chem.* **2018**, *13*, 108–112.
39. Den Hollander, M.; Bakker, C.A.; Hultink, E. Product Design in a Circular Economy: Development of a Typology of Key Concepts and Terms. *J. Ind. Ecol.* **2017**, *21*, 517–525.
40. Mestre, A.; Cooper, T. Circular Product Design. A Multiple Loops Life Cycle Design Approach for the Circular Economy. *Des. J.* **2017**, *20*, S1620–S1635.
41. Van den Berg, M.R.; Bakker, C.A. A product design framework for a circular economy. *PLATE (Product Lifetimes Environ. Conf. Proc.* **2015**, 365–379.
42. Moreno, M.; De los Rios, C.; Rowe, Z.; Charnley, F. A conceptual framework for circular design. *Sustain.* **2016**, *8*.
43. Shahbazi, S.; Jönbrink, A.K. Design guidelines to develop circular products: Action research on nordic industry. *Sustain.* **2020**, *12*, 1–5.

44. Post, N.L.; Bausano, J. V.; Lesko, J.J.; Case, S.W.; Duke, J.C. The role of durability in reliability-based design of composite materials for civil structures. *Sci. Eng. Compos. Mater.* **2005**, *12*, 153–158.
45. Kleemann, S.; Vietor, T. Design and dimensioning standards for multi-material components for the automotive industry considering their failure probability. *16th Eur. Conf. Compos. Mater. ECCM 2014* **2014**, 22–26.
46. Papadakis, N.; Ramírez, C.; Reynolds, N. 16 – Designing composite wind turbine blades for disposal, recycling or reuse. In *Management, Recycling and Reuse of Waste Composites*; 2010; pp. 443–457 ISBN 9781845694623.
47. Sassanelli, C.; Urbinati, A.; Rosa, P.; Chiaroni, D.; Terzi, S. Addressing circular economy through design for X approaches: A systematic literature review. *Comput. Ind.* **2020**, *120*, 103245.
48. Devadula, S.; Chakrabarti, A. Design strategies for circular economy. *Proc. Int. Conf. Eng. Des. ICED* **2015**, *1*, 1–9.
49. Post, W.; Susa, A.; Blaauw, R.; Molenveld, K.; Knoop, R.J.I. A Review on the Potential and Limitations of Recyclable Thermosets for Structural Applications. *Polym. Rev.* **2020**, *60*, 359–388.
50. Alzeanidi, N.; Ghasemnejad, H. Analysis of the effect of impact damage on the reparability of composite panels. *Compos. Struct.* **2017**, *176*, 304–312.
51. Otheguy, M.E.; Gibson, A.G.; Findon, E.; Cripps, R.M. Repair technology for thermoplastic composite boats. *Trans. R. Inst. Nav. Archit. Part B Int. J. Small Cr. Technol.* **2010**, *152*, 33–40.
52. Cong, L.; Zhao, F.; Sutherland, J.W. A Design Method to Improve End-of-Use Product Value Recovery for Circular Economy. *J. Mech. Des. Trans. ASME* **2019**, *141*, 1–10.
53. Asmatulu, E.; Twomey, J.; Overcash, M. Recycling of fiber-reinforced composites and direct structural composite recycling concept. *J. Compos. Mater.* **2014**, *48*.
54. Bank, L.C.; Arias, F.R.; Gentry, T.R.; Al-Haddad, T.; Tasistro-Hart, B.; Chen, J.-F. Structural Analysis of FRP Parts from Waste Wind Turbine Blades for Building Reuse Applications. In *Proceedings of the Advances in Engineering Materials, Structures and Systems: Innovations, Mechanics and Applications*; Zingoni, Ed.; Taylor and Francis group: London, 2019; Vol. SEMC 2019, pp. 1520–1524.
55. Fivet, C.; Brütting, J. Nothing is lost, nothing is created, everything is reused: structural design for a circular economy. *Struct. Eng.* **2020**, *98*, 74–81.
56. Job, S.; Leeke, G.; Mativenga, P.T.; Oliveux, G.; Pickering, S.J.; Shuaib, N.A. *Composites recycling: Where are we now?*; 2016;
57. Naqvi, S.R.R.; Prabhakara, H.M.M.; Bramer, E.A.A.; Dierkes, W.; Akkerman, R.; Brem, G. A critical review on recycling of end-of-life carbon fibre / glass fibre reinforced composites waste using pyrolysis towards a circular economy. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* **2018**, *136*, 118–129.
58. Pickering, S.J. Recycling Technologies For Thermoset Composite Materials. *Compos. Part A* **2006**, *37*, 1206–1215.
59. Papadakis, N.; Ramírez, C.; Reynolds, N. Designing composite wind turbine blades for disposal, recycling or reuse. In *Management, Recycling and Reuse of Waste Composites*; 2009; pp. 443–457 ISBN 9781845694623.
60. Roozenburg, N.F.M.; Eekels, J. *Productontwerpen, structuur en methoden*; 2e dr.; Lemma: Utrecht, 1998; ISBN 9051897065.
61. Hubka, V.; Eder, W. *Design Science*; Springer: London, 1996; ISBN 978-3-540-19997-7.
62. Ingemarsdotter, E.; Jamsin, E.; Kortuem, G.; Balkenende, R. Circular strategies enabled by the internet of things-a framework and analysis of current practice. *Sustain.* **2019**, *11*.
63. Pascoe, J.A. Slow-growth damage tolerance for fatigue after impact in FRP composites: Why current research won't get us there. *Procedia Struct. Integr.* **2020**, *28*, 726–733.
64. Nijssen, R.P.L.; Brøndsted, P. Fatigue as a design driver for composite wind turbine blades. In *Advances in Wind Turbine Blade Design and Materials*; 2013; pp. 175–209 ISBN 9780857094261.
65. ACEA - European Automobile Manufacturers Association Average age of the EU vehicle fleet, by country Available online: [https://www.acea.auto/figure/average-age-of-eu-vehicle-fleet-by-](https://www.acea.auto/figure/average-age-of-eu-vehicle-fleet-by-country)

- country/ (accessed on Aug 25, 2021).
66. Sumter, D.; de Koning, J.; Bakker, C.; Balkenende, R. *Circular economy competencies for design*; 2020; Vol. 12; ISBN 9789463663977.
 67. Brown, P.; Bocken, N.; Balkenende, A.R. Why do companies pursue collaborative circular oriented innovation? *Sustain.* **2019**, *11*, 1–23.
 68. Dorst, K.; Crabill, P. *Understanding design*; BIS Publishers: Amsterdam, 2003; ISBN 9063690401.
 69. Joustra, J.J.J.; Flipsen, B.; Balkenende, R.; Flipsen, S.F.J.; Balkenende, A.R. Structural reuse of wind turbine blades through segmentation. *Compos. Part C* **2021**, *5*.
 70. CEN - European Committee for Standardisation CEN/WS 113 Workshop on “Framework linking dismantled parts with new design components for the automotive industry in a circular economy model” Available online: <https://www.cen.eu/news/workshops/Pages/WS-2020-013.aspx>.
 71. Castaldo, R.; Falco, F. De; Avolio, R.; Bossanne, E.; Cicaroni Fernandes, F.; Cocca, M.; Di Pace, E.; Emanuela Errico, M.; Gentile, G.; Jásinski, D.; et al. Critical Factors for the Recycling of Different End-of-Life Materials : Wood Wastes , Automotive, Turbine Blades. *Polymers (Basel)*. **2019**, *11*.
 72. Zapelloni, G.; García Rellán, A.; Bello Bugallo, P.M. Sustainable production of marine equipment in a circular economy: deepening in material and energy flows, best available techniques and toxicological impacts. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2019**, *687*, 991–1010.
 73. Medici, P.; van den Dobbelsteen, A.; Peck, D. Safety and health concerns for the users of a playground, built with reused rotor blades from a dismantled wind turbine. *Sustain.* **2020**, *12*, 1–25.
 74. Shuaib, N.A.; Mativenga, P.T. Energy demand in mechanical recycling of glass fibre reinforced thermoset plastic composites. *J. Clean. Prod.* **2015**, *120*, 198–206.
 75. Poulidikou, S.; Jerpdal, L.; Björklund, A.; Åkermo, M. Environmental performance of self-reinforced composites in automotive applications - Case study on a heavy truck component. *Mater. Des.* **2016**, *103*, 321–329.
 76. Gao, C.; Yu, L.; Liu, H.; Chen, L. Development of self-reinforced polymer composites. *Prog. Polym. Sci.* **2012**, *37*, 767–780.
 77. Baldwin, C.Y.; Clark, K.B. *Design rules / Vol. 1, The power of modularity*; MIT Press: Cambridge, MA, 1999; ISBN 0262024667 9780262024662.